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Cybersecurity in the Danish water sector

How do Danish water utilities organize and execute cybersecurity incident response, and what patterns of practice and challenges emerge?

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Abstract

This thesis investigates the area of cybersecurity incident response (IR) within Danish water utilities. As cyberattacks increasingly threaten critical infrastructure, understanding practical IR approaches is crucial. This study addresses the research question *How do Danish water utilities organize and execute cybersecurity incident response, and what patterns of practice and challenges emerge?*

To answer this, a comparative multi-case study design was employed, involving scenario-based workshops with nine Danish water utilities collectively supplying 9% of the Danish population. Data was collected on key IR themes, including critical system identification, escalation, first actions, communication, roles and responsibilities, and reporting mechanisms.

A cross-case analysis was then conducted to identify patterns and challenges in their organizational and operational practices. These findings were compared to existing literature as we confirm, challenge and nuance previous understanding regarding IR in utilities within the water sector. The findings suggest that while initial isolation efforts are widespread and effective, challenges can arise as the incident is handed from operations to IT. During an incident Danish utilities has a preference for help from existing relationships over national assistance. Organizationally, utilities prioritize reputational considerations over direct economic consequences, which in return influence their approach for communicating to media and consumers during an incident. Communicative efforts are varied as some have an open approach with others being more closed. Finally, leadership of the IR team is usually delegated to IT, operations, or CEO roles. The Inclusion of specialized functions like economic, communicative and compliance personnel have an impact IR capabilities, suggesting that IR teams should be strategically designed to align with organizational objectives.

Moving forward, this study highlights several avenues for future research, including a deeper exploration of specific IR roles and communication approaches, further evaluation of workshop-based research methodologies, and broader studies at varying scales to understand knowledge flow and cross-national comparisons.

Keywords: Cybersecurity, Incident Response, Water Utilities, Cybersecurity Management, Scenario-based Workshop, Organizational Cybersecurity, Denmark

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We hope you enjoy the read.

- Alvin & Anton

Declarations

Use of Generative AI

Generative AI tools were used in the writing of this thesis. ChatGPT, Gemini, Claude, and Grammarly were used to provide feedback on written material, and assist with LaTeX formatting. Microsoft Word's AI transcription feature was used to convert audio recordings into text. All sensitive information was anonymized prior to using these tools.

All content, arguments, and findings are made by the authors.

Contributions

Both authors contributed equally to this project.

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1 Introduction

Water is essential to human survival, public health, and economic development. For centuries, societies have depended on access to clean drinking water and effective wastewater management systems to prevent flooding, control diseases, and protect ecosystems. Historical events linked to contaminated water, such as the six major cholera pandemics that killed millions of people in the 19th and 20th centuries, underline the critical importance of safe water infrastructure (WHO international, 2024).

The sixth goal of the UN Sustainable Development Goals calls for universal access to safe drinking water and adequate treatment of wastewater (UN Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2023). While some countries are still striving to build basic water and sanitation systems, more developed nations such as Denmark, members of the European Union, and the United States are now facing emerging threats to their well-established water sectors. Among these, cyberattacks pose a growing risk to the safety and reliability of critical water infrastructure.

The global water sector, like other types of critical infrastructure, is becoming increasingly exposed to cyber criminals due to advancements of technologies and vulnerabilities that can be exploited (Hassanzadeh et al., 2020). The consequences of such attacks range from temporary service disruptions or frozen systems to severe public health hazards and environmental damage. Given the essential nature of water supply and wastewater management, researchers describe the need for urgent attention from both policymakers and security experts when these incidents hit (ibid., 2020).

The increasing risk of cyberattacks on water infrastructure is now matched by stronger regulatory demands. While the water sector is already regulated in areas like water quality, environmental standards, finances, and data protection, it has only recently started receiving serious attention when it comes to cybersecurity. In contrast, sectors like finance and telecommunications have for years been subject to cybersecurity requirements. The upcoming NIS2 Directive, taking effect in Denmark in 2025, introduces stricter cybersecurity rules for critical infrastructure across the EU, including water utilities (*NIS 2 Directive* 2022; Styrelsen for Samfundssikkerhed, 2025). It expands the number of organizations covered and sets higher standards for risk management, incident handling, and accountability.

At the same time, after not being considered important for strategic cyber resilience by authorities a few years ago (Ministry of finance, 2018), the Danish Centre for Cybersecurity (CFCS) now classifies the water sector as high-risk, reflecting growing concern about its vulnerability to cyber threats (CFCS, 2025b). This concern is backed by real events. In December 2024, a cyberattack linked to pro-Russian hackers disrupted a Danish water utility, temporarily affecting service to several households (ibid., 2025). This change means that the cyberthreat level to the sector is now the highest it has ever been.

These developments are a key reason for this study. The timing of the NIS2 directive

and the rising threat level create a unique opportunity to explore how water utilities in Denmark are handling cyber incidents. Despite the urgency, there is still limited research in this area. Especially on how organizations actually will respond if they become victims of cybercrime.

In this study, we will investigate the area of cybersecurity related to incident response (IR) and the processes, roles, and governance when handling a cyber incident. Therefore, this thesis shifts the focus from formal policies to the practices of cybersecurity IR from an organizational perspective. Given that the regulatory structure is similar across EU member states, the findings may also hold relevance beyond Denmark.

1.1 Research question

This paper answers the following research question:

How do Danish water utilities organize and execute cybersecurity incident response, and what patterns of practice and challenges emerge?

To answer this, we conducted in total 27 hours of scenario-based workshop with nine Danish water utilities collectively supplying 9% of the Danish population (see table 7). These workshops were designed based on industry best practices regarding IR following the CIS control safeguards (Center for Internet Security, 2024). During the workshops, we examined how these utilities organize and execute key IR themes, including the identification of critical systems, escalation first actions, communication, roles and responsibilities, and reporting mechanisms. Following data collection, a cross-case analysis was conducted using matrices derived from the workshops. To understand the participants' reasoning and argumentation, we used transcriptions of recordings to support our findings.

This systematic approach allowed us to examine the identified IR themes across the nine utilities, enabling the emergence of patterns, similarities, and differences in their practice and execution. In the discussion, we compare our findings with existing research. This allowed us to confirm some known patterns, add new insights, and better understand how water utilities respond and handle cyber incidents. We also discuss how the different ways utilities organize and act during incidents can affect their overall preparedness, and we highlight some of the main challenges they face.

2 Background

This section provides background on the Danish water sector and its cybersecurity landscape to contextualize the study. It begins by outlining the overall structure of the sector, with a focus on medium-sized municipal utilities, to explain how water services are organized and delivered in Denmark. The important institutional stakeholders of DANVA, CFCS, and SektorCERT and their roles in knowledge sharing, incident monitoring, and national-level cybersecurity are then introduced. Finally, it addresses the increasing mix of IT and operational technologies (OT) to explain the background for one of the main drivers behind the rising cyber risk in the water sector.

2.1 Overview of the Danish water sector

In this study, the term Danish water utilities refers to companies responsible for delivering drinking water and/or managing wastewater (see fig. 1). Drinking water refers to the production, treatment, and distribution of clean water for household, industrial, and public use. Wastewater management includes the collection, treatment, and discharge of used water from homes, businesses, and stormwater systems to protect public health and the environment.

Figure 1: A typical urban water cycle showing drinking and wastewater management (U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, 2004)

The Danish water sector is highly decentralized and has a mix of a few large utilities, some medium, and a large number of micro utilities. For this study, we focus on the medium sized municipality owned *water utilities* which typically manage both wastewater

treatment and drinking water supply. Hereby, the many micro utilities, often operated by a few individuals or on a voluntary basis, are not within scope. The medium sized utilities often have multiple departments, more employees, and a broader operational setup compared to the local micro utilities. While some of these companies also provide additional services, such as waste management, gas, heating, or even electricity, our primary focus has been on their water operations. However, in cases where a utility company manages multiple services, some employees attending the workshop work across different fields, and their insights may reflect this overlap.

Since the 2009 water sector reform, both water and wastewater operations have been structured as independent private companies, fully owned by municipality entities rather than direct city departments (*Vandsektorloven* 2020). In larger cities, the water utility may cover multiple municipalities. In smaller towns, a single utility might handle the full water cycle of delivering potable water and treating wastewater.

Danish law requires full cost recovery for water services, enforcing a “*Rest in itself principle*”(Erhvervsstyrelsen, 2022) with no profits or losses. Utilities fund their operations via water tariffs and cannot profit, as any surplus is reinvested in the system. This framework has kept water services under public control rather than for profit. Even when utility operations are incorporated into private entities, municipalities retain control by appointing their boards and overseeing compliance with service and environmental standards (*Vandsektorloven* 2020).

Approximately 2/3 of Denmark’s drinking water is supplied by utility companies owned by 87 municipalities, either as independent municipal utilities or as joint companies serving multiple municipalities (see fig. 2) (Miljø- og Ligestillingsministeriet, 2025). The remaining comes from around 2,500 micro, consumer-owned cooperative water supply systems (*ibid.*, 2025). This distribution means that a small number of municipal utilities supply water to the majority of the population, while many micro utilities supply the remote areas.

Figure 2: Overview of utilities in the Danish water sector (Miljø- og Ligestillingsministeriet, 2025)

2.2 Danva, CFCS, & SektorCERT

In Denmark, three important actors assist on different levels in the advising, monitoring, and knowledge-sharing of cybersecurity within the water sector. These are CFCS, DANVA, and SektorCERT.

On the highest level, CFCS is Denmark's national authority for cybersecurity, under the Danish Defence Intelligence Service. Its main goal is to prevent, detect, and respond to cyber threats against Denmark's national security, including critical infrastructure (Forsvarsministeriet, 2025). CFCS advises and issues guidelines for all critical sectors, including the water sector, but it does not have an operational or sector-specific role. Its involvement with the water sector is mainly through national threat assessments, general guidance, and coordination on cyber preparedness at the national level (CFCS, 2025a).

There are two advocacy groups in the Danish water sector *The Association of Waterworks in Denmark* representing primarily micro utilities (Danske Vandværker, 2025) and DANVA, which represents the medium and large utilities (DK-VAND, 2024). We will only include DANVA's members for this study. Their goal is to support, represent, and strengthen the Danish water sector, and one of their areas of focus is on cybersecurity as part of protecting critical infrastructure. They do this by offering courses and network groups for strengthening the capabilities of its members (Mortensen, 2025).

SektorCERT is a Danish cybersecurity organization owned by industry associations representing critical infrastructure sectors such as district heating, electricity, and water, making DANVA one of its partners since 2023 (Mortensen, 2023). It is a CERT (Computer emergency response team) and operates 24/7 monitoring through endpoint detection and response (EDR) sensors installed at utilities, sending data to a central system to detect and respond to cyber threats (SektorCERT, 2024). They offer automatic monthly reports showing members a graphic of attempted attacks observed through their EDR sensors. While mainly focused on monitoring, SektorCERT also provides coordination support, expert guidance, and works with external IR partners. Participation is voluntary but strongly encouraged. DANVA members can use sektorCERT's sensors and support as part of their membership (Mortensen, 2023). This has made it accessible to smaller utilities lacking their own security operations. SektorCERT aims to act as a force multiplier by offering centralized protection instead of isolated efforts by individual companies.

2.3 Increasingly connected technologies

In water utilities, IT refers to business and administrative systems like office networks and billing databases, while OT covers industrial control systems that manage physical processes (Gunter, 2025). Important OT components include SCADA (Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition) software, programmable logic controllers (PLCs), and related sensors/actuators that regulate water treatment and distribution (ibid., 2025). Unlike

IT systems that handle data processing and communications, OT systems are designed to maintain physical operations. This difference means that availability and safety are the top priorities in OT environments, whereas IT security traditionally emphasizes data confidentiality and integrity (ibid., 2025). For example, a cyber incident causing a PLC outage could stop the water supply or treatment, posing immediate public safety risks.

However, in recent years, the water sector has increasingly begun to integrate IT and OT systems. This convergence enables improved data collection, remote monitoring, and operational efficiency, but it also introduces new cybersecurity risks, as threats originating in IT networks can potentially spread into sensitive OT environments (Grubbs et al., 2021).

3 Literature review

This chapter reviews existing literature relevant to understand, analyze, and discuss IR within Danish water utilities. The aim is to establish the current state of knowledge, identify research gaps, and provide a theoretical foundation for this study following a structure proposed by Bryman (2012, 102-109). The first part highlights the strategy used to identify relevant literature. Then key themes are presented, including the *water sector*, *infrastructure*, *small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs)*, *IR*, and *STS cybersecurity*. Finally, a sub conclusion highlights the research gaps which this thesis addresses.

3.1 Search strategy

To build an understanding of IR within Danish water utilities, we drew on a range of academic studies combined with professional literature from industry. Our literature search began by exploring existing research on cybersecurity within the water sector, with a particular focus on IR. No studies were found to investigate and compare IR in multiple water utilities. Given that we did not find any studies with exactly our focus, our review combines different themes that collectively produce a solid theoretical background.

We employed two complementary academic databases in the form of Google Scholar and the Royal Danish Library (Kb.dk) (see fig. 3). Google Scholar was selected for its broad coverage of global academic literature and its filtering function that isolates only literature review articles. This was complemented by the Royal Danish Library's database, which could give us a larger Danish selection and a filtering option for peer-reviewed content, allowing us to only examine articles of quality. This combination allowed us to identify broad trends using google scholar together with relevant papers from the Royal Danish Library with potentially comparable methodological approaches or focus.

Figure 3: Inclusion strategy for literature review

We developed a search string designed to capture relevant publications across four key areas (See table 1). First, it had to be related to the domain of cybersecurity. Second, it should include the water sector to narrow the sector. Third, it had to revolve around IR, reflecting our study’s focus. Lastly, a geographical parameter was added to capture regional cybersecurity considerations. This multidimensional search approach enabled us to identify literature that could aid us in answering our research question.

Theme	Cybersecurity	Sector	Focus	Geography
Search criteria	“cybersecurity” OR “information security”	AND “water sector” OR “water utilities” OR “water infrastructure”	AND “IR” OR “incident handling”	AND “Europe” OR “Denmark”

Table 1: Search Criteria Structured by Theme

We then chose to filter studies based on the year of publication. Given the significant changes in the water sector and the evolving external threat landscape, we limited our selection to studies published within the past ten years.

By using the search string on the two databases and applying the filters of respective literature review articles and peer review articles, we ended up with a total of 31 publications. 18 were found via google scholar, 16 via kb.dk, and three papers were found in

both (see fig. 3).

Titles and abstracts were screened to determine whether the work had been published in a reputable academic journal or appeared in less formal sources, which sometimes get through the filtering. An overview of the papers can be found in the table 2 below.

Author	Title	Year	Publication	Available	Type of Literature	Google Scholar	Kb.dk
Anglade, Boaz, et al.	LAC Post COVID-19: Challenges and Opportunities for Central America, Haiti, Mexico, Panama and the Dominican Republic.	2020	NONE	✓	Report	✓	X
Daousis, Spyridon, et al.	Overview of Protocols and Standards for Wireless Sensor Networks in Critical Infrastructures	2024	Future Internet	✓	Literature Review	✓	✓
Gonzalez-Granadillo et al.	Security Information and Event Management (SIEM): Analysis, Trends, and Usage in Critical Infrastructures	2021	Sensors (MDPI)	✓	Journal Article	X	✓
Gosine, Anil	Industrial Control Systems: Cyber Policies and Strategies	2020	Journal - American Water Works Association	✓	Report	X	✓
Grubbs, Robert, et al.	Evolution and trends of industrial control system cyber incidents since 2017.	2021	Journal of Critical Infrastructure Policy	✓	Literature Review	✓	✓
Hassanzadeh, Amin, et al.	A Review of Cybersecurity Incidents in the Water Sector	2024	Journal of Environmental Engineering	✓	Literature Review	✓	X
Hassib, Bassant, and James Shires.	Cybersecurity in the GCC: From Economic Development to Geopolitical Controversy.	2022	Middle East Policy	✓	Journal Article	X	✓
Hromada, Rehak, Lukas	Resilience Assessment in Electricity Critical Infrastructure from the Point of View of Converged Security	2021	Energies	✓	Method and case	X	✓
Boogaard, Joshua Ronald, et al.	Digital Twin Models for Cybersecurity Use Cases in Water Utilities and SCADA Systems: A Review	2024	Cyber Awareness and Research Symposium	X	Literature Review	✓	X
Fettig, Joachim, and Martin Oldenburg.	Overview: Preparedness in the Water Supply and the Sanitation and Sewerage Sectors in Germany and Europe	2019	Physical and Cyber Safety in Critical Water Infrastructure	X	Literature Review	✓	X
Knowles, William, et al.	A survey of cyber security management in industrial control systems	2015	International journal of critical infrastructure protection	✓	Literature Review	✓	X

Author	Title	Year	Publication	Available	Type of Literature	Google Scholar	Kb.dk
Kumar, Chetan, et al.	Cyber-physical Systems (CPS) Security: State of the Art and Research Opportunities for Information Systems Academics	2020	Communications of the Association for Information Systems,	✓	Journal Article	X	✓
Kumar, Sumit, and Harsh Vardhan	Cyber security of OT networks: A tutorial and overview	2025	NONE	✓	Literature Review	✓	X
Longo, Antonella, et al.	Cyber-Physical Resilience: Evolution of Concept, Indicators, and Legal Frameworks	2025	Electronics (Basel)	✓	Literature Review	X	✓
Lovecek, Tomas, et al.	Use Case of Water Reservoir Protection as a Critical Infrastructure Element in Slovakia Using a Quantitative Approach	2023	MPDI	✓	Article	X	✓
Malatji, Masike, et al.	Cybersecurity Policy and the Legislative Context of the Water and Wastewater Sector in South Africa	2021	Sustainability	✓	Journal	X	✓
Manzoor, Jawad, et al.	Cybersecurity on a budget: Evaluating security and performance of open-source SIEM solutions for SMEs	2024	PloS One	✓	Journal Article	X	✓
Michalec, Milyaeva, Rashid	Reconfiguring Governance: How Cyber Security Regulations Are Reconfiguring Water Governance	2022	Regulation & Governance	✓	Journal Article	X	✓
Mohammad Nasser al-Mhiqani et al	Insider threat detection in cyber-physical systems- a systematic literature review	2024	Computers and Electrical Engineering	✓	Literature review	✓	X
Olonilua, O., & Aliu, J. O.	Assessing Workforce Training Strategies in Critical Infrastructure: Insights and Recommendations.	2025	Institute for Homeland Security	✓	Literature review	✓	X
Osei-Kyei, Robert, et al.	Critical review of the threats affecting the building of critical infrastructure resilience.	2021	International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction	✓	Literature review	✓	X
Padilla-Gomez, Mario, et al.	Systematic Literature Review on Cybersecurity and its Influence on Cyber Attacks Targeting IoT Devices	2024	Computación y Sistemas	✓	Literature review	✓	X
Selvam, Damodar, and Anirudh Khanna.	Enhancing Utility Sector Efficiency and Security: Integrating Digital Identity Systems Amidst Privacy and Ransomware Challenges	2024	International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Communication and Technology	✓	Literature review	✓	X

Author	Title	Year	Publication	Available	Type of Literature	Google Scholar	Kb.dk
Shires, James, et al.	Middle East Cyber Security: Threats and Opportunities	2021	Middle East Policy	X	Journal article	X	✓
Takeda, Y., Ito, J., & Kawashima, Y.	Civil Defense in Japan: Issues and Challenges.	2023	Routledge	X	Book	✓	X
Tsybina, Eve, et al.	Smart cities: the data to decisions process	2025	Nature Cities	X	Not available	✓	X
Wells, Andrew, et al.	A Strategic Approach to Flood Risk Management	2021	The Journal of Critical Infrastructure Policy	✓	Journal Article	X	✓
William C. Merry, Sr.	Virtual networking cybersecurity and vulnerabilities in cloud computing applications: a systematic review	2023	NONE	✓	Literature review	✓	X
Wosnak, Wereda	Shaping Frugal Innovation Processes, and Ensuring Security and Sustainable Development of Enterprises in the Environment	2023	Sustainability (MDPI)	✓	Quantitative survey-based study	X	✓
Yigit, Yagmur, et al.	Generative AI and LLMs for critical infrastructure protection: evaluation benchmarks, agentic AI, challenges, and opportunities	2025	Sensors	✓	Literature review	✓	X
Zyoud, Shaher	Exploring the promising role of internet of things in urban water systems: a comprehensive global analysis of insights, trends, and research priorities	2025	Discover Internet of Things	✓	Literature review	✓	✓

Table 2: Literature found through the literature review

3.2 Key themes from literature

3.2.1 Water sector & critical infrastructure

Our review showed that most of the literature on cybersecurity in the water sector focuses either on national-level policy and governance (Anglade et al., 2020; Hassib et al., 2022) or on technical analyses of cyberattacks and specific IT/OT systems (Daousis et al., 2024; Grubbs et al., 2021; Knowles et al., 2015; Zyoud, 2025). However, we found very few studies that explore how water utilities respond to cyber incidents from an organizational perspective within the context of the sector.

Hassanzadeh et al. (2020) review 15 known cyber incidents in the water sector and show how both simple and advanced attacks have disrupted operations. They point to recurring vulnerabilities, like insider threats and weak access controls, and describe how many utilities lack internal expertise to deal with cybersecurity risks. Some of these

incidents reveal a pattern where national authorities typically intervene first following an incident, with crucial early warning signs remaining isolated within individual organizations rather than being shared systematically across the sector. Similar findings are presented by Grubbs et al. (2021) who focus more broadly on critical infrastructure, of which water utilities are included. They show how incidents often affect OT environments indirectly through IT compromises and how IT/OT integration increases the attack surface.

Other papers focus on the impact of regulation in cybersecurity. Michalec et al. (2022) focus on how cybersecurity regulation, specifically the NIS directive, is shaping the governance of the water sector in the UK. They show how implementation brings new actors into play and shifts priorities internally, often creating tension between operational staff, compliance requirements, and existing governance structures. The political aspect of cybersecurity is also examined by Malatji et al. (2021). They focus on the national cybersecurity strategies of South Africa and add a sector focus, highlighting a gap in sector-specific guidance and implementation in the water sector.

Other contributions are more conceptual or technical. Hromada et al. (2021) present a framework to assess resilience in energy infrastructure by looking at physical, cyber, and operational aspects together. It only mentions the water sector briefly, and the framework is not meant for the water sector. However, the integrated thinking is useful and reflects the kind of cross-functional focus we look for in our own research.

The studies we found provide useful perspectives, but none of them examine how water utilities organize their IR efforts through case studies.

3.2.2 Cybersecurity in SMEs

Another common theme in the literature was how SMEs face distinct challenges in managing cybersecurity, particularly when operating critical infrastructure, often stemming from resource constraints compared to larger organizations. Olonilua and Aliu (2025) highlight these constraints by observing that SMEs, compared to larger corporations, face limitations, especially regarding expertise and financial resources. The resource limitations inherent in SMEs directly impact their ability to implement and manage sophisticated cybersecurity. Manzoor et al. (2024) emphasize this, pointing out that SMEs often grapple with budgetary constraints and a lack of specialized cybersecurity expertise and personnel. By assessing the security and performance features of open-source SIEM systems, they help SMEs enhance their cybersecurity posture. Asadi et al. (2025) find similar considerations in their study of how SMEs demonstrate their security, and how different methods vary in cost, reliability, and accessibility.

This challenge of how SMEs practically manage cybersecurity with limited resources led us to consider research specifically focused on this context. Offering insight into how cybersecurity is organized and considering resource constraints within Danish SMEs, is the report by Kocksch and Jensen (2023), a paper encountered during cybersecurity

courses in our studies.

Contrary to some assumptions, Kocksch and Jensen's (2023) paper *Good Organizational Reasons for Bad cybersecurity* investigates the common perception that SMEs lack basic cybersecurity. Through an ethnographic study of 30 Danish SMEs, they reveal that while SMEs are concerned about cybersecurity, their approach is often dictated by practical and organizational challenges rather than a lack of awareness. The study finds that SMEs often implement cybersecurity measures, fulfilling basic recommendations or have critically assessed their cybersecurity situation, even if not adhering strictly to standard best practices. One major reason for these non-standard approaches relates to how responsibility is assigned.

They find that cybersecurity responsibilities in SMEs are typically integrated into existing roles rather than residing within dedicated departments or specialist positions. Kocksch and Jensen argue that resource constraints necessitate this distribution, with roles like IT managers, accountants, compliance specialists, or even external IT suppliers taking on cybersecurity duties alongside their primary functions. This distribution significantly impacts how cybersecurity practices are implemented and managed within the SME environment.

The specific professional background of the individual assigned cybersecurity responsibility introduces distinct advantages and challenges. IT managers possess a deep technical knowledge of the company's systems but may face conflicts when evaluating the systems they implemented. Accountants benefit from close ties to the CEO and an understanding of organizational processes but may lack technical depth. Compliance or communication specialists bring communication expertise but might lack familiarity with operational details. External IT suppliers often lack intimate knowledge of the company's internal workings and are limited to advisory roles. These inherent role-based dilemmas shape the practical cybersecurity landscape in SMEs.

The paper also discusses how practices are profoundly shaped by local rationalities. SMEs leverage their local resources, including long-term social relations, geographically limited operations, and small company sites, to develop specific tactics for upholding cybersecurity. This allows them to manage security, often effectively, through shared local knowledge, collective defense strategies, and the flexible handling of rules. In this context, deviations from formal cybersecurity rules are frequently viewed not as failures, but rather as necessary local adaptations to ensure operational efficiency and maintain workable processes.

They conclude with several recommendations for how cybersecurity initiatives within SMEs, with the final being *"Staying aware of how moral high grounds and the 'shaming' of insufficient cybersecurity measures create obstacles to constructive dialogue"* (Kocksch et al., 2023, p. 4). This insight into the importance of trust and avoiding judgment has been a useful consideration in shaping this thesis.

3.2.3 Incident response

Effective IR demands specialized workforce training, especially for critical infrastructure personnel in SMEs. Olonilua and Aliu (2025) highlight that cybersecurity training, of which IR is included, is vital for adapting to threats. Especially, they see potential in simulation-based training for replicating real-world scenarios safely and cost effective. This approach directly addresses the need for enhanced readiness in resource-constrained environments like many of the medium sized water utilities.

Building on individual preparedness, effective response also hinges on organizational structure, particularly the coordination between IT and Operations. Balancing IT and OT responses is crucial for effective incident handling in critical infrastructure. Gosine (2020) makes this argument in their report on resilience in the water sector. Separate IT and OT governance hinders communication and unified action during crises, making IR less effective. He argues that bridging this divide through joint structures and interdisciplinary skills is essential, as cyber threats increasingly span both domains, and uncoordinated responses can worsen impacts. Integrated IT/OT IR is therefore fundamental for resilience in the water sector.

Beyond the specific challenge of IT/OT integration, the broader operational aspects of responding require practical guidance. Guidance for the operational aspects of IR often stems from professional literature rather than academic sources. Kumar et al. (2020) observe that practical advice from consultants and experts typically informs operational responses. Common recommendations include having response teams, conducting exercises, and defining roles, although effective coordination remains a key challenge. Furthermore, they highlight that communication *"represents the main challenge to an effective operational response to cyberattack"*(Kumar et al., 2020, p. 686). This highlights the value for water utilities in referencing established best practices from the professional field to build their response capabilities.

Several studies highlight the role of professional literature, such as cybersecurity frameworks. We also draw on these in this study. Cybersecurity frameworks help translate best practices into practical tools and structures that organizations can use (CCSI Contemporary Computer Services Inc, 2020). Widely adopted standards like the NIST Cybersecurity Framework (CSF) and its associated control set, NIST Special Publication 800-53, as well as ISO standards, are often used by larger organizations and are common in academic discussions. However, the Center for Internet Security (CIS) Controls offer a more accessible set of controls for many smaller companies with fewer resources.

3.2.4 STS cybersecurity

Cybersecurity research increasingly recognizes the importance of organizational and human-centered approaches. While much of the literature still focuses on technical risk modeling, awareness training, or compliance-based evaluations, there is a growing body of work that

explores how organizations make sense of and respond to cyber threats in practice.

Hassanzadeh et al. (2020) touch upon risk perception in water infrastructure systems through simulations and threat modeling, showing how different stakeholders assess vulnerabilities. Michalec et al. (2022) take an interpretive approach inspired by science and technology studies, focusing on coordination, trust, and sensemaking in cyber crises. A central theme in this text is the existence of different *social worlds* like IT, engineering, and management, each with its own priorities and logic. These studies illustrate how cybersecurity is not only a technical issue but also rooted in organizational routines and decision-making processes.

Although our research is not based on the same theoretical traditions, we share a similar interest in exploring cybersecurity through the lens of practice and organization. Rather than focusing on perception or post-incident interviews, our workshop-based method investigates how water utilities structure their IR. Our use of structured scenario workshops with cross-case comparison allows us to investigate sector-specific patterns while preserving the contextual richness of each case. This will be elaborated in section 4.5 Cross-case analysis.

Our research contributes to the growing field of empirical cybersecurity studies by offering an alternative method for capturing how organizations prepare for and reflect on cyber incidents. The structured comparison of multiple utilities builds on this methodological turn, while being grounded in applied, practice-oriented research.

3.3 Sub conclusion

This literature review established the theoretical foundation for cybersecurity in water infrastructure, SMEs, IR, and STS, revealing a research gap in IR practices among Danish water utilities.

Although the reviewed material offered useful context regarding sector-specific challenges, resource limitations common in smaller organizations, and broad IR principles via the use of frameworks, it revealed an absence of studies examining the execution of IR and indicated that research into IR organizing is still emerging. This necessitates our study with its focus and methodological approach to examine the practices and execution of IR within Danish water utilities, addressing some of the gaps in the current literature.

4 Methodology

This chapter presents the methodology used in the study. It outlines the research design, company and participant selection, the workshop structure, data collection, and analytical approach. In addition, it includes reflections on methodological considerations, such as the role of the researcher, and concludes with a walkthrough of how the workshops were conducted in practice.

4.1 Research design & strategy

This study is based on a comparative case study design involving nine on-site workshops, each conducted with a separate Danish water utility. The utilities reflected diversity in size, organizational structure, and technical infrastructure within our scope. The data that we derived from the workshops was first digitized from pictures of the analog workshop outputs and categorized so that similar outputs could be compared across the utilities. The use of structured workshops and standardized tasks further supports consistency and comparability of the workshop output across cases. Recordings of the workshops were used to support and better understand the reasoning behind the workshop output data. The outputs were later analysed using a case-oriented cross-case analysis, inspired by Miles and Huberman (1994) and Khan & VanWynsberghe (2008). The cross-case analysis used the method of *stacking comparable cases* into themes forming thematic matrices.

These themes were selected deductively, as we built the workshops on the basis of the CIS Control 17, it made sense to relate the themes of the workshop to the themes of the analysis. However, some themes were selected as they emerged from participant input. This approach allowed us to get both insight into each individual case and the identification of broader patterns.

Figure 4 shows the chronological process of the study, which will be accounted for in this methodology section.

Figure 4: Overview of the research process from sampling to findings.

4.1.1 Comparative case study design

This research adopts a qualitative comparative multi-case study design with cross-sectional elements. By combining elements from different research design archetypes, we provide a structured qualitative examination, allowing for a nuanced understanding of IR within Danish water utilities.

A comparative multiple-case study approach analyzes several companies as individual cases. As Bryman argues that “*we can understand social phenomena better when they are compared in relation to two or more meaningfully contrasting cases or situations*”(Bryman, 2012, p.72). We subscribe to this notion and believe that this approach allows for the identification of patterns and contrasts to provide a richer and potentially more generalizable understanding than a single case study.

This study also incorporates elements of a cross-sectional research design. Bryman explains that “*In cross-sectional design research, data on the variables of interest are collected more or less simultaneously*”(Bryman, 2012, p. 59). While our data collection spanned several months through workshops, the time mattered less as the workshops did not change. Thus, each utility went through an identical scenario, thereby creating simultaneous comparable data. Although cross-sectional designs are usually quantitative, a qualitative approach is genuine as well, as Bryman states that “*qualitative research often entails a form of cross-sectional design*”(Bryman, 2012, p. 62). Therefore, cross-sectional elements are present in our research design as each utility was exposed to the

same scenario and have produced a similar output.

An important advantage of this cross-sectional design element is enhanced comparability. Establishing variation between cases requires systematic and standardized data collection (Bryman, 2012). The workshops were designed with clear, concrete outputs (see section 4.4.1 Workshop output & audio recordings as units of analysis), ensuring systematic and standardized data collection across all cases.

4.1.2 Reliability, replicability, & validity

When evaluating social science research, Bryman (2012) emphasizes the three aspects of the reliability, replicability, and validity of a study .

Reliability is defined as “*whether the results of a study are repeatable*” (Bryman, 2012, p.46). In our study, all nine workshops followed the same format, scenario, and had the same tasks. Individual recordings of the discussions varied and could likely not be repeated as the same people would likely not bring up the same discussions multiple times in repeated scenarios. However, the structured framework of the workshop output ensured that similar types of data were produced in each case, which is very likely to be repeated. This enabled us to maintain a degree of reliability.

Replication refers to “*whether the study can be replicated by other researchers*” (Bryman, 2012, p.46). Because we used a predefined workshop script and documented both the structure and the analysis method, other researchers could replicate our approach with similar types of organizations. While specific results may differ depending on local context and team composition, the method itself is replicable.

Validity is about “*whether an indicator really measures the concept it is supposed to be measuring*” (Bryman, 2012, p.46). Our aim is not to measure a fixed outcome but to understand how utilities organize and execute IR during a cyber incident. The goal is that our data reflect realistic and grounded responses. However, we will at most be measuring a simulation of an incident, meaning that we will never know exactly how the utilities respond to an incident. Internal validity is strengthened by combining workshop outputs with quotes from workshop transcriptions. External validity is more limited, since we only include nine cases, but the goal is analytical generalization and to provide insights that may be useful for similar organizations, not to generalize statistically.

4.1.3 Mixed reasoning methods

This study uses both deductive and inductive reasoning to explore IR in a way that allows for both structure and openness.

The workshop activities were not created randomly or purely exploratively. The content in the workshop was chosen carefully, and the data collection through the workshops was designed “*on the basis of what is known about in a particular domain*” (Bryman, 2012, p.24). By incorporating an established framework like the CIS 17 control and seeking

expert sources in SektorCERT and CFCS, we learned about sector-specific information and best practices. This approach enabled a structured data collection focused on aspects of IR that were generally seen as relevant. We then transitioned to a more inductive approach (Bryman, 2012, p.24-27) for data analysis, allowing themes and nuanced understandings regarding various IR dimensions to emerge directly from the workshop outputs and participant discussions. In the discussion, we combine both deductive and inductive thinking. We compared our results with existing research to see what matched, what differed, and what added something new. At the same time, we pointed out new ideas and gaps that came from our own data. This mix helped us build a base for answering our research question.

4.2 Participants, scope, & sampling

This section outlines how we identified, approached, and engaged with Danish water utilities for participation in our study. Our goal was to ensure a methodologically sound selection process while also building trust and relevance through early engagement with sector stakeholders. We begin by describing the knowledge-building activities and initial meetings that helped shape our workshop design. Then, we explain how we defined the scope of our study and selected relevant companies through sector segmentation and expert input. Finally, the process of contacting utilities and recruiting participants for the workshops, including the strategies used to gather a diverse and comparable group of personnel across organizational roles, is presented.

4.2.1 Knowledge gathering, initial meetings, & workshops

To design a methodologically strong and practically relevant study, we conducted a range of meetings and engagement activities throughout the thesis process. These engagements helped us build sector-specific knowledge, refine our workshop format, and gain trust from the water utility involved.

The activities can be grouped into four types. First, we focused on knowledge gathering with domain experts and initial contact meetings with individual utilities to explain the project and understand their context. Then, the workshops themselves which served as the core data collection method. Finally, we had follow-up contacts, where we would collect missing information.

Table 3 below gives an overview of the timeline and structure of these engagements during the months of this research.

#	Organization	Topic	Month
1	Company (later excluded)	Initial meeting	October 2024
2	Company (later excluded)	Initial meeting	November 2024
3	Company (later excluded)	Initial meeting	November 2024

#	Organization	Topic	Month
4	Case company (lacked resources)	Initial meeting	November 2024
5	DANVA	Background water sector meeting	November 2024
6	Case company	Initial meeting	November 2024
7	Case company	Initial meeting	November 2024
8	Danish industries	NIS2 & European cybersecurity	November 2024
9	Industriens Fond	Cybersecurity in SME's and existing projects.	November 2024
10	Danish Environment Agency	Cybersecurity reports water sector	November 2024
11	Case company	Initial meeting	December 2024
11	SektorCERT	Cybersecurity in the water sector	January 2025
12	Case Company	Initial meeting	January 2025
13	Center for Cybersikkerhed	Cybersecurity in the watersector	January 2025
14	Case Company	Workshop	January 2025
15	Case Company	Discussion about potential online participation	January 2025
16	Case Company	Workshop	January 2025
17	Case Company	Workshop	January 2025
18	Case Company	Initial meeting	March 2025
19	Case Company	Initial meeting	March 2025
20	Case Company	Initial meeting	March 2025
21	Case Company	Initial meeting	April 2025
22	Case Company	Workshop	April 2025
23	Case Company	Initial meeting	April 2025
24	Case Company	Workshop	April 2025
25	Saga Labs	Experiences with workshops	April 2025
26	Previously attacked utility	Experiences from IR	April 2025
27	Case Company	Workshop	April 2025
28	Case Company	Workshop	April 2025
29	Case Company	Workshop	May 2025
30	Case Company	Workshop	May 2025
31	Case Company	Follow-up	May 2025
32	Case Company	Follow-up	May 2025
33	Case Company	Follow-up	May 2025
34	Case Company	Follow-up	May 2025

Table 3: Engagement and data collection activities

4.2.2 Finding our scope within the sector

The point of departure for choosing organizations for this study was the NIS2 regulation (see fig. 5). The NIS2 directive has multiple sectors within its scope defined as being either essential or important (Digitaliseringsstyrelsen, 2025), with each sector having a distinct set of requirements, although not clarified yet at the time of writing this paper. From these, we found the sector of water, including drinking as well as wastewater, of special interest. This was due to the criticality when their services are unavailable, together with known stories about previous incidents.

Figure 5: NIS2 impacted sectors with focus on water sector (Mohan, 2024).

For finding relevant companies, we primarily used two methods. The initial strategy we used was finding relevant companies through the CVR register via proff.dk, as it allows for finding information about companies based on their size and sector. Later, we changed strategy to include DANVA’s members in general.

Figure 6: Segmentation tools from Proff.dk (proff.dk, 2025)

We visited proff.dk and used their segmentation functionality (see fig. 6). The first

step in segmentation was choosing the sector. We selected the categories “*Vand og kloak*” (Water and sewer), “*Vandbehandling*” (water treatment), along with “*Vandforsyning*” (water utility), which gave us a total of 9,104 companies. This segmentation allowed us to focus on water-related organizations, covering everything from drinking water supply to sewage and wastewater management. We then filtered the results based on the number of employees. We wanted to exclude the largest as well as all the micro utilities, and therefore excluded all but organizations between 40 and 300 employees. Lastly, we segmented to only work with the main units “*Kun hovedenheder*”, so we wouldn’t get subsidiaries of larger companies, but only the SME’s. This left us with a total of 127 companies (see fig. 7).

Figure 7: Filtering process on Proff.dk to identify water utilities

To gain insights into the sector, we had discussions with representatives from DANVA, CFCS, the Danish environment agency, and SektorCERT to understand the sector better. These consultations revealed key differences between the Danish drinking water and wastewater sector, which we had not considered previously. We learned that when referring to “water” in the industry jargon, it always meant drinking water, whereas wastewater would sometimes be called “dirty water” or simply “waste water”. Additionally, we understood why it was messy to investigate the CVR register on Proff.dk. This was because some water utilities within our scope operated as single entities but were officially registered with multiple subsidiaries, with each having a separate CVR number, causing them to be excluded from our segmentation.

Based on these insights, we adjusted our focus solely to *water utilities* for heightening similarity between the organizations for more robust results. Consequently, this meant that three companies, of whom we had already established contact, had to go, as they were operating commercially within the private sector, focusing on sewage, and could negatively impact the results.

We learned that companies that were members of DANVA were generally the type of utility that fitted with our desired type of organization. We found a publication detailing the water quality of many members (DANVA, 2024), which we ploughed through to reach out to the remaining companies within our scope. This process resulted in a final selection of 76 water utilities providing either drinking water, wastewater, or both.

4.2.3 Contacting utilities & preparing for workshop

The following section provides a simplified and idealized overview of how we engaged with utilities in our project. The process was more chaotic in practice and involved multiple iterations and back-and-forth adjustments.

The first step was to connect with the right people within each organization. Our primary target was the Head of IT, or a similar position, as they typically had both an interest in the topic and the decision-making capability to allocate resources for our workshop. Additionally, these roles were often accountable for the NIS2 implementation in the utilities, which meant they easily understood the concepts and would likely be supportive of the project.

The first point of contact was an email introducing the project (see appendix, 1.A). This email outlined key details, including the purpose of the initiative, the workshop structure, expected outcomes, and the approximate resource commitment required from the utility. When available, we sent the email directly to the IT manager, (water) operations manager, and the CEO. If direct contact was unavailable, we used the company's general email address.

Two to three days after sending the email, we followed up with a call. This allowed us to assess their interest, clarify any questions, and ensure our mail had reached the right person.

For companies that expressed interest, we scheduled a 30-minute pilot meeting (See appendix 2.B). This meeting focused on explaining the project's background, objectives, and the level of involvement expected from participants. For us, it simultaneously served as an opportunity to gain insights into each company and the sector. At the end of the pilot meeting, we worked with the utility to set a date for the workshop. This process is illustrated in fig. 8.

Figure 8: Recruitment and participation process

While cyber incidents typically originate through IT systems, their effects often extend beyond the IT department. This broader organizational impact is central to our investigation. To capture a wide range of perspectives, we invited a diverse group of participants, asking each utility to involve 2–6 employees likely to play a role during a cyber incident. Suggested roles included IT, Finance, Compliance, Communications, Operations, and the CEO. This inclusive approach promoted interdisciplinary insight but also introduced challenges, such as differences in cybersecurity expertise when ensuring active participation from non-technical stakeholders.

Table 4 shows the organizational roles represented by workshop participants. These roles, standardized from a variety of original titles, are presented with a brief description of their functions, alongside a count of how many filled each position.

Group	Role	Description / Title	Count
CEO	Chief Executive Officer (CEO)	Overall strategic and executive leadership of the utility	2
IT	Head of IT (HOF IT)	Leads the IT department and is responsible for strategic IT decisions	6
	IT Employee	Day-to-day IT staff handling systems, support, and maintenance	8
	Chief Information Security Officer (CISO)	Oversees cybersecurity policies	1

Group	Role	Description / Title	Count
Operations	Head of Operations (HOF OPS)	Responsible for managing daily operational processes	5
	Operational Employee	Field or plant staff who operate water infrastructure	11
Other	Chief Financial Officer (CFO)	Oversees budgeting, accounting, and financial risk management	2
	Compliance Employee	Ensures adherence to laws, standards, and regulations	2
	Communication Employee	Handles communication, media relations, and stakeholder messaging	3
	Other	Any additional internal role not categorized elsewhere	5

Table 4: Roles participating in the workshop

4.3 Workshops as a research methodology

The primary research approach employed in this paper is the use of workshops as a methodology following a scenario-based structure. The following section will justify this approach theoretically by defining its definition, key characteristics, its implications for data collection, and the role of the researcher.

Ørngreen and Levinsen (2017) define workshops as “*arranged events of a limited duration targeted to participants who either share a common domain (...) or share agendas*” (Ørngreen et al., 2017, p. 72). They further highlight several defining characteristics common to workshops that shape their structure and facilitation. Firstly, workshops are typically facilitated by individuals with expertise in the relevant domain, ensuring knowledgeable guidance. Secondly, active participation is a core expectation as attendees are encouraged to contribute, challenge assumptions, and shape discussions, often drawing directly from their daily work experiences. Thirdly, workshops are goal-oriented, with both participants and organizers anticipating specific outcomes, which can range from developing new insights to proposing concrete redesigns of processes or policies. These characteristics collectively contribute to the effectiveness of workshops in generating rich data.

Ørngreen and Levinsen (2017) examine how workshops can be used as a methodological framework. Through a literature review, they define and present three distinct approaches to their use in academic contexts. These are workshops as a means, workshop as a practice, and finally workshop as a research methodology. These approaches have implications for the “*goals, outcomes, phases, roles, and organization*” (Ørngreen et al., 2017, p. 72) of the subject being studied. For this thesis, the specific approach adopted is workshops as a research methodology.

The primary focus of the workshop as a research methodology approach is “*on the study of domain-related cases using the workshop format*” (Ørngreen et al., 2017, p. 72). Workshops of this type are designed to fulfil two goals simultaneously. First, it is to

meet participants' expectations of achieving something in their own interest, like gaining insights and discussing their practices. Second, it serves an explicit research purpose by producing "*reliable and valid data about the domain in question*" (Ørngreen et al., 2017, p. 72). This dual focus has therefore been a priority when designing the workshops, to ensure that we could collect rich data while participants also achieved something valuable.

To better understand the distinct nature of the Workshop as a research methodology approach, the two other types identified in the paper must be presented. Workshop as a means is designed to achieve a specific goal, often addressing issues within a research domain. Literature on this type broadly focuses on either tools for designing and conducting workshops or new ideas and knowledge resulting from them. In contrast, Workshops as a practice focus on workshop forms and outcomes. This type often has a developmental dimension, as participants frequently create something that is subsequently examined. Although these have interesting aspects, the workshop as a research methodology approach is adopted due to the dual nature of relevance for participants and producing reliable data.

4.3.1 Data output

The data produced with the workshops as a research methodology approach differs significantly from that obtained through methods like observation or interviews. Through structured activities and facilitated interactions, the participants themselves become the "*data-producing apparatus*" (Ørngreen et al., 2017, p. 73). The authors argue that this is unique compared to more traditional types of research methods. While observations offer direct insights into actions and interviews provide access to individuals' reasoning, workshops "*combine a little of both without being either*" (Ørngreen et al., 2017, p. 78), creating a space where insights emerge from collaborative engagement with scenarios.

Referencing Darsø (2001), the authors distinguish between primary and secondary data. Primary data consists of the artifacts produced by participants during the workshop activities, as well as recordings of the sessions. For this paper, this will be in the form of post-it notes and forms produced, collectively referred to as the workshop output, together with transcriptions of audio and video recordings of the sessions. Primary data is considered less influenced by participants' recall, thereby mitigating a layer of "*subjective interpretation*" (Darsø, 2001, p. 221). In contrast, secondary data are gathered mainly through post-workshop interviews with participants. The use of primary data as the main unit of analysis is a strength of this study.

4.3.2 Scenario & the dual role of the researcher

The duality of the workshop as a research methodology also presents itself in the dual role of the researcher. Again referencing Darsø (2001), Ørngreen and Levinsen (2017) argue that there is a distinction between the roles of the clinician and the ethnographer.

The clinician is primarily focused on the needs of the participants or clients, adapting the process to suit them even if it means deprioritizing research objectives (Darsø, 2001). In contrast, the ethnographer's role is to prioritize the generation of scientific knowledge, with less regard for participant needs (ibid., 2021). This has been a consideration throughout the study, especially prevalent when designing (see section 4.4.2 Designing the workshop) and when conducting the workshops (see section 7.1 Limitations).

The use of a scenario-based structure for workshops has implications for the research. Scenario based workshops create a space where participants collaboratively engage with presented issues. This facilitated, interactive setting transforms the workshop into “*a place for collaborative negotiation of meaning*”(Ørngreen et al., 2017, p. 78). Through these scenarios, “*workshops bring us close to practice without being in practice*” (ibid., 2017). Together with the previously general characteristics of collecting data through workshops, this allows for the identification of new factors and their relationships, which would be difficult to uncover through traditional data collection methods. Hereby, the use of workshops as a research methodology following a scenario allows us to examine the complex nature of IR.

4.4 Data collection & workshop design

This section outlines how data was collected for the study and the considerations that shaped the workshop format. It describes both the types of data generated during the workshops and the rationale behind the design choices made. First, we explain the primary data sources used for analysis, which are the structured workshop outputs and transcribed audio recordings. Then we elaborate on how the workshops were designed.

4.4.1 Workshop output & audio recordings as units of analysis

The primary units of analysis for this study are the structured output generated by participants during the nine workshops, as well as transcription of the audio recordings from each.

This structured output consists of the physical or written materials produced collectively by participants during the exercises. These include participant-filled forms and post-its placed on pre-designed matrices which were produced during the workshop and written out afterwards (see fig. 9). The consistent format of these outputs across all workshops facilitates the creation of themes and reliable cross-case comparison of the data. The material from each workshop can be found in appendix 2.

In addition to this visual and written output, all workshop sessions were recorded to capture the discussions that informed participants' decisions. These recordings were crucial for understanding the “how” and “why” behind specific choices and provided essential context for the written output. While video recording was initially used, it was discontinued after the first few workshops in favor of audio-only recording, as being

Figure 9: Illustrative examples of workshop outputs

videotaped did not suit all participants. The audio recordings from all workshops were transcribed using Microsoft Word’s transcription tool. These transcriptions are used to support the workshop output, help clarify intent and resolve potential ambiguities, as well as allowing for insights into reasoning.

The workshops were divided into eight distinct themes with corresponding exercises based on the nine safeguards regarding IR of the CIS framework. Each of these sections was specifically designed to produce an output that would be comparable across the participating water utilities, facilitating a later cross-case analysis. These themes addressed the following areas: *Priority of Systems, Escalation, Consequences, Roles and Responsibilities, First Actions, Communication, Reporting, Internal/External Responsibilities, and Reflections* (see fig. 10).

Figure 10: Data from workshop

4.4.2 Designing the workshop

When designing the workshop, we had a number of considerations that influenced its final form.

To ensure the scenario was relevant, we consulted with SektorCERT, DANVA, the Danish Environment Agency, and CFCS to, among other things, discuss common attacks within the sector. These consultations provided valuable insights into the operational context of water utilities, notably the interplay between IT and OT. SektorCERT and CFCS highlighted ransomware and attacks targeting SRO systems, the Danish abbreviation for Styring, Regulering og Overvågning (control, regulation, and monitoring systems) as prevalent threats. This was the primary reason leading to the selection of a ransomware attack on a SRO system as the workshop scenario. The workshop design underwent iterative refinement based on feedback from these organizations to enhance realism and incorporate their areas of concern, such as an emphasized importance of communication.

To provide a structured and industry-relevant focus on IR, we aligned the workshop exercises with Control 17 of the CIS Controls v8.1 framework that provides nine concrete safeguards outlining best practices for effective incident response (Center for Internet Security, 2024). The workshop exercises were designed to cover the actions specified in the first eight safeguards of CIS Control 17 so that all exercises within the framework had a safeguard justifying it (see table 5 and table 6). These safeguards fall within tiers one and two of the framework, which are applicable to organizations like the participating water utilities for whom a *”loss of public confidence if a breach occurs”* (Center for Internet Security, 2024, p.7) is a concern. We held a test workshop, where we found safeguard 17.9 created confusion and produced weak data. Simultaneously, this control is only targeted at larger organizations, so it was excluded from the final design.

Safeguard	Description	IG1	IG2	IG3	NIST CSF Security Function	Included in Workshop
17.1	Designate Personnel to Manage Incident Handling	✓	✓	✓	Respond	✓
17.2	Establish and Maintain Contact Information for Reporting Security Incidents	✓	✓	✓	Govern	✓
17.3	Establish and Maintain an Enterprise Process for Reporting Incidents	✓	✓	✓	Govern	✓
17.4	Establish and Maintain an Incident Response Process		✓	✓	Govern	✓
17.5	Assign Key Roles and Responsibilities		✓	✓	Respond	✓
17.6	Define Mechanisms for Communicating During Incident Response		✓	✓	Respond	✓
17.7	Conduct Routine Incident Response Exercises		✓	✓	Recover	✓
17.8	Conduct Post-Incident Reviews		✓	✓	Recover	✓
17.9	Establish and Maintain Security Incident Thresholds			✓	Recover	X

Table 5: CIS Control 17 Safeguards mapped NIST CSF (Center for Internet Security, 2021) and workshops inclusion.

Maintaining participant engagement was a design consideration to ensure active contribution and generate rich data. To achieve this, we incorporated variety into both the types of tasks participants were asked to perform and the methods by which information was delivered. Post-it exercises were used when generating or discussing multiple elements, allowing for easy grouping and rearrangement. Pen-and-paper activities were used when a more structured and unison outcome was needed. Lastly, facilitated open discussions were used to encourage the exchange of opinions, lowering the stakes for expressing perspectives.

Relevant information to the scenario or exercises was also delivered using varied methods to maintain interest. These included written text presented on slides, physical handouts delivered as mail in envelopes, and information read aloud via speakers. We used the physical space as some exercises were conducted either standing by a whiteboard, sitting down, or split into smaller groups. Additionally, Breaks were strategically placed within the workshop flow and utilized to foster informal conversation and gather further insights from participants.

Finally, we wanted to ensure the workshops produced tangible, written output suitable for our analysis. Each exercise was specifically crafted to result in concrete written outputs, like a written communication plan. This deliberate design choice aimed to generate primary data that could be directly analyzed, minimizing the reliance on retrospective data.

4.5 Cross-case analysis

In this section we draw on literature from Khan and VanWynsberghe (2008) and Miles and Huberman (1994), outlining the theoretical background for cross-case analysis. Then we present our practical implementation of the method used in the analysis.

4.5.1 Cross-case analysis & stacking comparable cases

Cross-case analysis was selected as the primary method for analyzing the qualitative workshop data. This method is valuable for this study as it allows for the examination of multiple cases that participated in the same structured scenario and generated similarly structured output, highlighting variations in practice despite similar conditions. Also, the cross-case analysis allows us to manage the large volume of data generated from the workshop outputs and 27 hours of workshop recordings to produce interpretable and meaningful findings.

Our approach is grounded in the theory provided by Khan and VanWynsberghe (2008) and the practical guidance offered by Miles and Huberman (1994).

Translating this conceptual strategy into a concrete method, we utilize the practical guidance using *An expanded sourcebook: Qualitative data analysis*, Miles and Huberman (1994). A key concept in their cross-case method is “*stacking comparable cases*” (Miles

et al., 1994, p. 176), through the use of matrices and meta-matrices. Meta-matrices are described as “*master charts assembling descriptive data from each of several cases in a standard format*” (Miles et al., 1994, p. 178). The core principle involves juxtaposing condensed, relevant data from each case side-by-side to enable both in-depth understanding within each case and the identification of patterns across cases. The goal is not only summaries of individual cases, but the systematic identification of differences, similarities, and potential explanatory patterns across the full set of cases.

To carry out the analysis, we first organized the data from each utility into themes based on the structure of the workshop. We then created six comparison matrices, where we grouped answers from each utility and found patterns. To test our method, we started by analyzing the output from the same utility separately, and each created a matrix for every theme to see if we would code the data in the same way. The results were similar, which gave us confidence to use this approach for the rest of the cases. We then created a meta-matrix, which collects the main patterns and gathers “*multiple tables to one big one that has considerably condensed the original data*.” (Miles et al., 1994, p. 180). This allowed us to see if there are trends on a larger scale that say more about the utilities across themes. The meta-matrix is the final part of the analysis, as they put it, “*The meta-matrix is a condensation of previous matrices - not a first step.*” (Miles et al., 1994, p. 180). This cross-case analysis method hereby allows us to keep the unique context of each utility’s response while simultaneously conducting a structured comparison across all nine utilities.

4.5.2 Implementing cross-case

For the structure of the analysis, we rely on Miles and Huberman’s (1994) practical framework, which emphasizes the use of matrices and displays. This allows us to systematically compare cases across shared thematic categories while still preserving the unique context of each utility.

The initial steps involved structuring, transcribing, and organizing the workshop data into a format suitable for analysis. After each session, we structured the workshop output from each utility by writing out post-its and forms into separate, standardized slide deck formats (see fig. 11 for an example). This process created case files for each company, providing a full view of each company’s responses across all the workshop themes and enabling us to understand the data in context.

Based on the workshop’s structure, we then created a series of six thematic matrices. In each of these matrices, utilities are represented as rows, and categories within the theme are the columns. We populated these matrices with the relevant data extracted from the standardized workshop output slide deck. This process of structuring and populating the thematic matrices aligns with what Miles and Huberman refer to as “*stacking comparable cases*” (Miles et al., 1994, p. 173), laying out data from each case in a structured display.

Our analysis is structured around the thematic matrices. We reviewed the matrices to

Figure 11: Process from workshop data to thematic cross-case matrix .

interpret the data, identify trends, differences, and potential clusters across companies. For instance, by examining the "first actions" matrix, we observed patterns in initial responses, noting that the majority of utilities had a similar immediate response, as will be elaborated in the analysis. These observed patterns form the basis for a more detailed interpretation and comparison.

To support and deepen this matrix-based interpretation, we turned to the transcription of the audio recordings. Here we selected direct quotes that clarified, expanded upon, or challenged the patterns and interpretations derived from the matrices. As Miles and Huberman note, "*direct quotations can serve as vivid examples to support the analyst's assertions*" (Miles et al., 1994, p. 265), and proved useful in understanding the rationale behind participants' reasonings, adding depth to our findings.

Finally, we summarize our findings by constructing a meta-matrix. In this overview, we are able to visualize patterns on a broader scale. This allowed us to see sector-wide tendencies and important case-level distinctions simultaneously. This meta-matrix provides a structured basis for "*seeing rather than just looking*" (Miles et al., 1994, p. 176) across cases, facilitating the final stage of the analysis.

4.6 Walkthrough of workshop

The following pages describe how we conducted each of the workshops. We tried to balance two roles of being active clinicians who made sure the workshop was useful and engaging for utility staff and being ethnographers who observed and gathered data in a consistent way. Figure 6 below shows an overview of each individual part of the workshop, displaying time allocated, topics, medium, and which safeguards it is built upon (See appendix 1.C for full slide deck, 1.D for material printed material).

Section	Time	Acc. Time	Time ID	Topic	Medium	CIS Control
0. Intro	10	10	6	0.1	Introslide	Slide
			3	0.2	Purpose	Slide
			1	0.3	Agenda	Slide

Section	Time	Acc. Time	Time	ID	Topic	Medium	CIS Control
1. Important systems	20	30	4	1.1	Write down systems	Post-it	
			15	1.2	Prioritization of systems	Post-it	
2. Reporting Process	15	45	2	2.2	What is IR?	Slide	
			1	2.3	Irregularities in SRO	Slide + print	
			10	2.4	Reporting process	Form	17.3
3. Consequences	15	1:00	2	3.1	Unreliable sensors	Slide + print	
			10	3.2	What are the consequences?	Post-it	
Break	10	1:10					
4. Roles and Responsibilities	25	1:35	2	4.1	Ransomware	Print	
			5	4.2	Lead? Is payment an option? Contingency plan?	Form	17.1
			15	4.3	Responsibilities	Form	17.4, 17.5
5. First Actions	20	1:55	3	5.1	List of actions	Post-it	17.4
			15	5.2	Prioritize actions	Post-it	
6. Communication	20	2:15	2	6.1	Message from SektorCERT	Slide + audio	
			15	6.2	Communication plan	Form	17.2, 17.4, 17.6
7. Reporting / External Help	20	2:35	2	7.1	Message from CFCS	Slide + print	
			15	7.2a	Reporting to authorities	Form	17.4
				7.2b	Recovery	Marker	
Break	10	2:45					
8. Evaluation	15	3:00	5	8.1	Note learnings	Post-it	17.8
			10	8.2	Group learnings	Post-it	

Table 6: Full workshop plan by theme, time, exercise, and CIS 17 safeguard.

4.6.1 Introduction & system identification

Each workshop began with a dedicated introduction section. This involved a brief introduction to the project by our primary organizational contact, followed by a round of participant introductions where everyone shared their role and expectations for the session. This initial engagement aimed to foster involvement throughout the workshop and provided valuable insight into group dynamics we should be aware of. We then introduced the workshops, with a clinical focus, emphasizing its purpose and relevance for them as a utility, particularly in light of the expected NIS2 regulation. To build confidence and underscore the session's quality, we highlighted that exercises were built upon in IR best

practices using the CIS framework and mentioned that conversations with DANVA, SektorCERT, the Danish Environmental Agency, and CFCS guided its design, reinforcing the legitimacy and specific relevance of the workshop for their type of organization.

Following the framing, we initiated the first exercise session. This exercise was designed for accessibility, allowing contributions regardless of technical expertise. Participants were given 3-5 minutes to write down systems used at the utility, whether IT, OT, or other types, on individual post-it notes.

Next, participants were instructed to prioritize these identified systems based on two parameters. The identified systems would then be prioritized on a 3x3 matrix as illustrated in fig. 12. The X-axis represented the temporal aspect of *How long can the system be unavailable before it negatively impacts operations?*. This was divided into three categories, which were *minutes/hours*, *days*, and *weeks*. The Y-axis captured the business criticality, guided by the question *How essential is the system to the company's ability to maintain its core activities?*. This was categorized simply as *low*, *medium*, or *high*. Participants then used this matrix as a visual tool to place their post-it notes, positioning each system according to its assessed downtime tolerance and business importance.

Figure 12: System prioritization matrices and anonymized digitalized form

The exercise gave us an understanding of the systems while establishing a risk-based thinking pattern, helping the participants recognize that certain systems within their utility are inherently more critical than others.

4.6.2 Getting hit by ransomware

The second and primary section of the workshop focused on navigating an incident scenario. Given the diverse backgrounds and roles of participants, we first provided a concise overview of the purpose and key steps involved in IR (Alexander Nelson et al., 2025).

Escalation

We then launched the scenario, which began with an employee discovering irregularities within the SRO system. The initial task presented to the group was to collaboratively

design the ideal chain of contacts for reporting this irregularity internally and navigate in the complexity, having limited information. This exercise directly addressed establishing a robust IR process, aligned with principles aligned with CIS safeguard 17.3. about the process for reporting incidents.

Participants were guided to answer the three questions of *Who should the employee report to?*, *How should it be reported?*, and *What information should be reported?*. To facilitate this, one participant was selected to document the group's answers (see fig. 13).

Figure 13: Physical reporting form and anonymized digitalized version.

Consequences

Next, we gave them a bit more insight into what was happening as they learned that the sensors and their data were now deemed untrustworthy, requiring reliance solely on manual verification due to the connection to the compromised SRO system. At this point, the participants did not yet know that the irregularities were due to a cyber attack, so we asked them to reflect on potential consequences in plenum. Concrete questions asked included *How long and how can you maintain operations without access to the SRO system?* and *What is the worst-case scenario for A) the company?, B) customers?, and C) partners?*

Following this discussion, we held a short break. Here, we would ask clarifying questions to better understand the organization and the participants' perspectives.

Roles & responsibilities

This next phase of the workshop focused on establishing roles and responsibilities in an escalating crisis, aligning with CIS safeguard 17.1 about assigning personnel, 17.4 about establishing an IR process, and 17.5 about the responsibilities of roles.

This was the part of the workshop where we showed the participants a ransomware message stating that hackers had infiltrated their systems. The scenario specified: *While your team is investigating, a ransomware message appears on an operator's workstation connected to the ICS, indicating that your OT (Operational Technology) may also be*

compromised. The severity of this development was underscored by physically delivering the ransomware note to a participant in a sealed envelope (see fig. 14).

Figure 14: The hacker message and the envelope it was given in for dramatic effect.

Recognizing the gravity of the attack, they had to escalate to a state of emergency. This was guided by a form designed to clarify the initial crisis response (see fig. 15).

Figure 15: Allocation of roles during escalation form and anonymized digitalized version.

Following this emergency, the task shifted to defining the relevant people for handling the incident. Given that such an attack broadly impacts the organization, we aimed to identify the team that would be assembled and assign responsibility for managing specific incident-related areas. These areas were *Economy, Communication (Internal and External), Overall Lead, IT, Operations, Compliance*, and an *others* column for additional personnel. Furthermore, they had to establish whether the person noted was aware of their responsibility (see fig. 16). The individual identified as the Lead in the preceding discussion would ideally serve as the typist for this exercise.

It is worth noting that throughout the workshops, we removed a planned final row in this section intended for participants to list uncertainties within each designated area. This adjustment was made because participants found the task unclear, disrupting the flow, and resulting in low-quality data for that specific point.

First actions

Figure 16: Responsibilities and incident response team (physical and digital)

The next task for the participants was to react to the ransomware scenario. This exercise was built on top of the CIS safeguard 17.4 about establishing an IR process. Recognizing the amount of information previously presented, we began with a brief recap of the scenario’s progression this far.

The exercise was structured in two distinct parts. First, participants individually brainstormed and noted down the specific actions they believed were necessary in response to the attack.

Second, participants gathered around a whiteboard for a collective prioritization effort based on their individual notes (see fig. 17). The resulting prioritized list was organized along two dimensions. The Y-axis introduced a temporal aspect, dividing the first 24 hours after an incident into five distinct phases of response. The X-axis represented a spectrum, requiring participants to place actions based on whether they were primarily technical or organizational in nature. We initiated this collaborative placement by simply asking for a good candidate for the very first action, allowing the discussion to flow organically, limiting our role to timekeeping. The choice of post-its was deliberate for this part, as their ease of movement and rearrangement facilitated ongoing negotiation and collective decision-making on prioritization via placement on the whiteboard.

Figure 17: First actions exercise from workshop and anonymized digitalized version.

Communication

The subsequent part of the workshop tasked participants with creating a communication plan informing relevant stakeholders (see fig. 18).

To effectively initiate this exercise, we played a voice message imitating an employee from SektorCERT. This message explained the importance of informing relevant key stakeholders about the situation, setting the stage for the task, which was guided by CIS safeguard 17.2 on contact information, 17.4 on establishing the IR process, and 17.6 on mechanisms for communication during IR.

Figure 18: Communication exercise output and anonymized digital version.

The form was structured in a table format. Each row began with a specific stakeholder or group of stakeholders in the first column, followed by a box designated for specifying what information they need to know. Furthermore, they had to create the three most important communication channels during an incident.

Reporting and External help

Participants were presented with a final piece of information designed to add pressure. We increased pressure with a message from CFCS stating that the participants had to report the incident, as well as keeping them updated on their contingency plan. The message concluded with a potential ultimatum stating that if their contingency plan was not sufficient, CFCS would take over until operations were back to normal.

Due to this dual request, the final exercise of the scenario involved splitting the participants into two groups, completing different exercises. This division was implemented to simulate the limited resources available when an incident strikes. This added some pressure, which would likely be present during a real incident. The division for the two parallel exercises was handled by the designated lead from the roles and responsibilities exercise.

One group focused on NIS2 compliance through practicing formal reporting, guided by CIS safeguard 17.4 on establishing the IR process. For this, we used a physical recreation of CFCS's cyber incident reporting form (CFCS, 2025c). The group's task was to fill out a twelve-page form, gaining hands-on experience with the level of detail required for an initial report (see fig. 19 for example and appendix 1.D for full form). Although

participants largely drove this somewhat bureaucratic task, we provided minor assistance where needed, as physically replicating an online form proved occasionally confusing. Based on guidance from CFCS, we were told that the future reporting form for NIS2 would be similar to the NIS1 reporting form.

Figure 19: Reporting exercise output and digitalized version

While one part of the participants filled out the reporting form, the other part concentrated on the recovery aspect of the IR. Their task was to examine the organization’s reliance on external support for restoring systems after a breakdown. This involved re-visiting the system matrix created during the first exercise (see fig. 20). Using this matrix, they were asked to mark each system to indicate whether the responsibility for recovery relied on internal capabilities, external assistance, or a combination. This provided the organization with an overview of its dependencies on external parties during an incident. Following the completion of these two exercises, we held a second break.

Figure 20: System prioritization with and without responsibility

4.6.3 Evaluation & reflections

The final phase of the workshop was dedicated to reflection as prescribed in CIS safeguard 17.8 about post-incident reviews. Participants were given three minutes to individually capture their responses to the question *What insights, considerations, and reasons for action have you gained in the last three hours?*. Following this individual reflection period, we collectively reviewed and discussed the points noted on the post-its as a group (see fig. 21).

Figure 21: Reflection exercise fictional workshop output

After the reflection exercise, we provided a recap highlighting how each exercise was specifically designed to enhance their IR capabilities. The final notion was to let them know that they would receive our research paper after completion, along with a presentation of the findings contextualized for their organization.

Finally, we thanked everyone for participating. As they packed up, we had a last opportunity for informal conversations to gather their thoughts and overall impressions.

4.7 Sub conclusion

This chapter has outlined the methodological foundation of the study, including our research design, data collection strategy, and analytical approach. By using a structured, scenario-based workshop format and combining deductive and inductive reasoning, we were able to gather rich, comparable data from nine Danish water utilities. The cross-case analysis method allowed us to identify both individual practices and broader patterns across the sector. While this approach offered valuable insights, it also involved certain limitations that will be discussed later in section 7.1 Limitations. Together, these choices provide the basis for addressing our research question in the following analysis chapters.

5 Analysis

This chapter presents the results of our cross-case analysis of how nine Danish water utilities organize and execute IR. The initial section shows a display with characteristics of the organizations which are part of the study (see table 7), to give context to the analysis. The rest of the analysis draws on structured workshop output and audio transcripts, and is structured around six themes that align with the workshop design. The analysis reveals a mix of shared practices and differences, and looks at how organizational setup, internal processes, and assumptions influence IR efforts. The analysis chapter concludes with a cross-case meta-matrix, building on the main findings across all themes and utilities to provide a condensed understanding of sector-level tendencies and key areas of variation.

5.1 Organizational characteristics

Table 7 provides a descriptive case overview of organizational characteristics as proposed by Miles and Huberman (1994). The utilities in the table are anonymized, and details are purposely vague, to show an anonymized overview of key organizational characteristics for the nine participating utilities.

Utility	Ownership	Water customers	Employees	IT Setup	In-house IT department	Cyber contingency plan	Cyber-insurance	Water	Waste-water	Other utility types
A	Municipality	50-100k	200-400	Mixed	3-5	X	✓	✓	✓	Heating + Waste
B	Municipality	10-20k	<50	Mostly internal	3-5	X	X	✓	✓	Heating + Waste + Electricity
C	Municipality	20-50k	50-100	Mixed	0	✓	X	✓	✓	Waste
D	Municipality	20-50k	50-100	Outsourced	3-5	X	X	✓	✓	Waste
E	Private with some municipality	50-100k	>400	Internal	>25	X	✓	✓	X	Heating + Electricity
F	Municipality	>100	>400	Mixed	Unknown	X	✓	✓	✓	Heating + Electricity + Gas
G	Municipality	10-20k	<50	External	<2	✓	X	✓	✓	None
H	Municipality	<10k	50-100	Mixed	<2	✓	✓	✓	✓	Heating
I	Municipality	>100	100-200	Mixed	3-5	✓	X	✓	✓	Gas + Heating

Table 7: Anonymized organizational characteristics of participating utilities

At their core, the utilities share key similarities. All participants provide drinking water services, and the great majority also manage wastewater. Furthermore, they share ownership structure, with all but one utility being municipality owned.

However, the utilities also show organizational variations. Their scale varies widely as they supply a range of consumers from below 10,000 up to over 100,000 consumers. This diversity is mirrored in their organizational size, ranging from smaller utilities with fewer than 50 employees to larger ones employing more than 400.

Their IT setup and internal capacity also differ. Utilities have different IT setups including internal, external, and mixed arrangements. This diversity is reflected in the size of their in-house IT departments, which range from zero in-house employees to larger ones, with more than 25 employees.

Variance is also found in the presence of a formal cyber contingency plan and cyber-insurance. Only one utility employs both measures, one had none, with the remaining seven having one of these measures in place.

Lastly, utilities vary in their operational scope. While some focus solely on water and wastewater services, others are multi-utilities, also supplying heating, waste, electricity, or gas, adding layers of complexity.

Collectively, these characteristics reveal that while the utilities share core similarities in ownership and primary services, they exhibit significant organizational variation, notably in size, IT structure, and capacity. These organizational characteristics will provide context for understanding the types of organizations in the study.

5.2 Thematic cross-case analysis

The following analysis examines how Danish water utilities organize and execute incident response across the six key themes of *System reliance*, *Escalation*, *First actions*, *Communication*, *Roles and responsibilities*, and *Authority involvement*. Each theme corresponds to a distinct section of the workshop, enabling a structured comparison. A central pattern that emerges across cases is that despite the presence of formal guidelines and regulatory expectations, much of the actual response work relies on practical experience, internal coordination, and improvisation. Rather than following rigid plans, staff often act quickly based on their understanding of local systems and past incidents.

Note on how to read utility references

In the analysis, we refer to utilities using anonymized identifiers (e.g., Utility A, B, F). These references are used to illustrate patterns across cases and do not carry analytical significance within or across themes. Readers are not expected to track which utility did what. The focus is on shared practices, not individual behaviors.

5.2.1 System reliance

The first task in the workshop asked participants to identify their key systems and consider the business criticality of the system to be able to operate. At the same time, they would also be considering the time it would take before a breakdown of a system would have an impact on operations. They then determined who would be responsible for getting each system back up and running. They could choose either internally, externally, or through a mix of both.

The matrix in table 8 shows an overview of how the utilities categorize their systems. It includes the ratio of where the responsibility lies during a breakdown (internal, external, and mixed), the responsibility for SRO/SCADA systems, and who holds responsibility for the most critical systems. The matrix also identifies which systems were considered highly important and time-sensitive (within minutes or hours) and which were classified as lower priority, with operations tolerable for weeks following breakdown.

Utility	Internal systems / all ratio	External systems / all ratio	Mixed systems / all ratio	SRO/SCADA responsibility	Responsibility for highly critical systems	Criticality: minutes/hours	Criticality: Low priority and weeks
A	$\frac{5}{14}$ - Some internal reliance	$\frac{7}{14}$ - Some external reliance	$\frac{2}{14}$ - Very little mixed reliance	External	Mostly external	Phone system, SRO, AQUIS	Economy system, Empl
B	$\frac{6}{14}$ - Some internal reliance	$\frac{3}{14}$ - Little external reliance	$\frac{5}{14}$ - Some mixed reliance	Mixed	Equal between internal and internal	SRO, Network, power grid	Envidrift, Sertica
C	$\frac{10}{15}$ - Big internal reliance	$\frac{4}{15}$ - Little external reliance	$\frac{1}{15}$ - Very little mixed reliance	External	Internal	DHCP, DC	Economy system, Powerbi, Windows, Intra
D	$\frac{3}{23}$ - Very little internal reliance	$\frac{14}{23}$ - Some external reliance	$\frac{6}{23}$ - Little mixed reliance	Mixed	External mostly	TELE, Internet, Network, Contingency plan, COT-wastewater treatment plant	ESDH, GDPR portal, Time registration tool, waste disposal system
E	$\frac{9}{21}$ - Some internal reliance	$\frac{1}{21}$ - Very little external reliance	$\frac{11}{21}$ - Some mixed reliance	Mixed	Mixed mostly, internal secondly	OT, PLC, SRO, Windows, ABB, AIA/ADK, SELOMEGA, I/O	Economy system, Empl
F	$\frac{7}{16}$ - Some internal reliance	$\frac{6}{16}$ - Some external reliance	$\frac{3}{16}$ - Little mixed reliance	Internal	Internal only	AD Control, Water SCADA, OT manual control, PLC in SRO	NONE
G	$\frac{3}{17}$ - Very little internal reliance	$\frac{13}{17}$ - Big external reliance	$\frac{1}{17}$ - Very little mixed reliance	External	Mostly External	Mapsystem, electricity, supplier systems, Windows, Citrix, TDC, Blue Idea, Intranote	Adobe package, Word-Press, Live connect
H	$\frac{0}{10}$ - No internal reliance	$\frac{10}{10}$ - Only external reliance	$\frac{0}{10}$ - No mixed reliance	External	External	Fiber Network and SRO	Docunote
I	$\frac{0}{28}$ - No internal reliance	$\frac{2}{28}$ - Very little external reliance	$\frac{26}{28}$ - Very big mixed reliance	Mixed	Mixed	HMI - local control	Facebook, KMD, Blue Idea, TS, Contracts, CMS, M365, Control Manager, Time reg

Table 8: System prioritization and responsibility in participating utilities

When examining the categorization of internal, external, or mixed responsibilities across utilities' systems, the findings were mixed, revealing different dependencies on external vendors during potential breakdowns. The majority of utilities (Utility A, B, C, D, E, G, H, I) had some external reliance listed within their most critical and time-impactful category. This initial overview establishes that reliance on third parties for the most crucial systems is a common factor, inherently introducing complexity in IR capabilities compared to purely internal setups.

Utilities showed general unity in their prioritization of critical systems. Systems identified as highly critical were predominantly related to OT and core infrastructure, such as SRO, SCADA, PLC, tele coverage, internet, and electricity (Utility A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H, I). There was a strong consensus that these were the crown jewels, whose failure would immediately jeopardize their core services. As one participant stated after placing PLC and SRO on the matrix, *"It has to run. it is critical. We have luckily been a bit anticipatory and made it possible to run in island mode, but it requires people to be stationed"* (Utility H, appendix 3).

On the other end of the scale are administrative and support systems like economy systems, PowerBI, and document systems. These were considered less business critical and would take longer before negatively impacting core operations, expressed by one employee as *"losing our economic system? Yes, we can probably still operate"* (Utility E, appendix 3). While their loss is a disturbance, service delivery can continue. However, the placement of systems sometimes caused minor arguments, revealing nuances in defining criticality. One participant questioned the high criticality of an IT system for water delivery *"Why? I would like to contest that a bit. Why is that critical in regard to delivering water to the consumers"* (Utility G, appendix 3) while the counterargument highlighted that the system could *"become the blocking factor for everything else we do in the business which actually makes it the most critical"* (Utility G, appendix 3), showing criticality can be defined by indirect dependencies as well as direct impact. That is, OT and core infrastructure are primarily seen as the most critical, with administrative systems being considered less critical and can therefore be out of service for a longer time.

4 utilities had a heavy reliance on external support if systems broke down, as half or more of their systems had an external vendor responsibility (Utility A, D, G, H). In these cases, critical systems such as SCADA, network infrastructure, or contingency planning tools are managed partly or entirely by external partners. This setup indicates a level of dependence on third parties, which could impact their ability to act quickly and independently during a cyber incident.

Some of the smaller utilities relied on external partners to manage their critical systems. Two utilities (Utility G, H) rely almost fully on external actors to manage their most critical systems. This suggests limited internal technical capacity and a need to rely heavily on vendors during an incident. Correlating this with the organizational characteristics (see table 7), we see that these are smaller utilities measured in both staff and

the in-house IT department. A reasoning behind this was external reliance adjusts for a lack of internal personnel, with the expectation that someone else possesses the necessary resources and experience. A participant from Utility G exemplified this, stating, “*We’ve kept almost everything external... we don’t have people who can do this. We just reach out to our vendors.*” (Utility G, appendix 3). However, this reliance on external partners was also seen at one of the larger utilities. This was explained by one employee “*We are a large organization compared to some, but in reality, it’s a small organization. That means having the competencies in-house to manage, develop, and handle all those systems is completely impossible*” (Utility I, appendix 3). This was viewed as a strategic strength, as highlighted by the statement “*If we had to know everything about all the systems ourselves, it would make us incredibly vulnerable*” (Utility I, appendix 3). This suggests that some utilities, especially the smaller ones, may be more dependent on external actors out of necessity, which could impact their ability to act quickly and independently during a cyber incident. Alternately, some larger ones might view it as a deliberate strategy to leverage specialized knowledge.

In contrast to heavy external/mixed reliance, a significant group of utilities maintains stronger internal responsibility for their most critical systems. Three utilities (Utility C, E, F) indicated more internal responsibility for their most critical systems. Here we find both larger utilities (Utility E, F), but also the smaller utility C was part of this, meaning that internal capabilities exist in different sizes of organizations. A participant stated the importance of having some internal control, even on external systems, stating “*We can’t do everything ourselves, but we can decide how it should be done, and what it should look like*” (Utility B, appendix 3) and emphasizing the desire “*We want to have so much control over the things we manage in-house that we’re able to ask the right questions*” (Utility B, appendix 3). This internal approach, where external reliance is viewed with caution, is seen as a strength as they have greater control, enabling a quick response.

The differences we observed in the responsibility structures, ranging from full external reliance to strong internal control, show a perspective of how the organizational setup may influence the ability to respond effectively to a cyber incident. The exercise revealed significant variation in how utilities perceive system criticality and assign responsibility, highlighting a strategic divide between reliance on external vendors and building internal capacity, each with distinct implications for IR speed, control, and resilience.

5.2.2 Escalation

In the workshops, we were curious about how technical irregularities usually get reported further up the ladder in the organization. We suspected that a cyber incident would most likely first be noticed on an operator’s computer at a non-management level, making it important to examine how such information travels upward to decision-makers. The matrix in table 9 illustrates how utilities’ technical staff initially react to and escalate an irregularity upon discovery, capturing the early stages before the incident is identified

as a cyberattack. The data comes from early in the workshop scenario, where they do not yet know that it is a cyber incident, and instead it should illustrate a general system issue, and thus provides insight into the utilities' standard problem-handling procedures.

The thematic matrix for this section is structured around five key elements. The medium of initial escalation, e.g., phone, email, verbal report. The first point of contact describes who is initially informed. The final contact in the chain is who ultimately receives the information. The amount of contacts in the chain describes the number of individuals involved in the escalation path, and the information describes the content of the message typically communicated. Together, these dimensions reveal how escalation procedures differ across utilities and highlight the organizational dynamics that shape early IR.

Utility	Medium for initial escalation	First chain of contact	IT after operations in chain of contact	Last chain of contact	Amount in the chain	Information to be reported
A	Phone or QMS	Head of operations	✓	Reality: IT, Ideally: IR Team	Reality: 5, Ideally: 3	What (context), when (timeline), and why (reason)
B	Phone	Head of operations	✓	IT	3	When did it start?, Is it still a problem?, What is affected?, and Importance
C	Not reported	Management	✓	IT	2	What do we know?, what do we suspect?, and IT is trying to figure it out.
D	Phone	Head of operation	✓	External IT	3	Which station?, does everything physical on the location work?, and IT disturbance?
E	Orally or mail	Operational employee	✓	CFCS	5	Placement of station, consequences, how many affected?, and when can they expect normal operation?
F	Phone or QMS	Nearest leader	X	Nearest leader	1	Rootcause and how to contain the problem momentarily?
G	Phone or verbal	Operational employee	✓	Water and IT operations	2	What he sees / Experiences, Is it hardware?, and Is it software?
H	Phone	Head of Operations	✓	Head of IT	3	Things don't deliver normally/as they should
I	Phone	Operational employee	X	PLC vendor	3	SRO data and possible analysis of problem

Table 9: Overview of incident escalation and information processes

Diverse quantity of steps & a clear structure

The matrix reveals notable differences in the number of contacts in the escalation chain when utilities escalate system irregularities. The length of the escalation chain varied from only a single (Utility F) and up to five contacts (Utility E, A). This variation likely reflects differences in organizational complexity and reporting structures. While we could observe that these escalation chains differed in length, we did not get clear indications from discussions on why this was the case, and if any considerations had been put into the number of contacts in the chain.

Utilities with shorter escalation chains may be able to react faster in the early stages of an incident. However, this could lead to less coordination or missed documentation. Longer chains might support a more structured process, but could slow down urgent decisions. We did not see clear evidence of these effects during the workshops, but the differences suggest a possible trade-off between speed and coordination that could matter during real incidents.

During the workshop, we generally found a clear structure and understanding about how to escalate due to the nature of their work. Reporting such irregularities was treated as routine and largely unremarkable. Participants approached it as part of their daily operations, expressed by a participant “*that’s a very daily operating situation*” (Utility F, appendix 3). Because of this familiarity, initial reporting often goes to an immediate supervisor (Utility A, B, D, E, F, G, H, I) such as the head of Operations or SRO responsible, rather than to IT. One company broke this pattern as the irregularity had to escalate directly to management (Utility C). The information shared in these early stages tends to be simple and direct because both parties share the same technical language and domain knowledge. This process may be effective for routine OT issues. However, it becomes more fragile when the incident involves or transitions into the IT domain.

Challenges arise when going from operations to IT

Once escalation reaches the boundary between operations and IT, where knowledge and responsibility must be passed, utilities often encounter significant friction that can spark discussion. IT was typically in the escalation chain after operational leadership (Utility A, B, C, D, E, G, H), and this handover was frequently problematic. The boundary represents a critical challenge in the IR process, highlighting difficulties in transitioning responsibility and information flow between the traditionally separate operational and IT domains during a crisis.

This handover friction manifests in several specific issues during the escalation process. One key challenge involves the lack of clarity or overlap between operational and IT contingency plans. Some utilities acknowledged this gap, questioning their own plans, such as asking, “*Is there any overlap between the IT contingency plan and the drinking*

water safety contingency plan?” (Utility F, appendix 3), while others admitted cyber incident planning had not fully extended to operational systems stating, *“we haven’t reached the water yet on cyber incidents”* (Utility A, appendix 3). Furthermore, communication breakdowns and differing perspectives on urgency were common friction points. In one utility, the handover of a critical issue from operations to IT created a heated discussion where an IT employee questioned the urgency of the incident if operations would hand over an issue. In the workshop, the IT employee stated *“The importance. I usually ask that too, because there’s no reason for me to jump into my work clothes and drive out here when in reality it can wait until tomorrow”* (Utility B, appendix 3). This created tensions because the operational staff emphasized they would always already make an initial assessment in such a situation, *“But we have assessed that before we call”* (Utility B, appendix 3). Another side of the handover was the fact that there exists a reluctance within operations to involve IT too quickly due to a fear of it being a false alarm and potentially creating a crying wolf effect for future, genuinely critical cyber events, with one participant noting, *“if you then say every time, well, I think we have a cyber incident, then the day there is something then...”* (Utility F, appendix 3) leaving the remaining group agreeing.

These points of friction show a broader challenge in coordinating responses between operations and IT departments. Cyber incidents in critical infrastructure often affect both areas, meaning they require cooperation between teams that usually work separately. While most utilities have clear plans for regular emergencies managed by operations, cyber incidents are different as they often involve systems and knowledge from both IT and operations. This creates confusion when plans, responsibilities, and communication structures are not aligned. These challenges may reflect cultural differences, missing joint procedures, or a lack of shared understanding between the teams. This connects to how IR is organized, showing that unclear boundaries in the handover from OT to IT can weaken the overall response.

Empowering the man on the ground

Within many utilities, there is a prevalent organizational culture that values direct action and operational autonomy over stringent and bureaucratic reporting processes. Several utilities expressed a strong preference for simple, direct communication during incidents. Some utilities actively work to bridge the mentioned operations/IT gap, for instance, by creating dedicated roles to prevent IT staff from being isolated *“So that we don’t have any IT people sitting inside their own cheese dome”* (Utility F, appendix 3) as one employee explained his role. Separately, when discussing escalation pathways in general, participants often expressed skepticism towards complex hierarchies and bureaucratic procedures. There was a strong emphasis on empowering the man on the ground to take immediate action. Concerns were raised about the dangers of delays caused by

waiting for decisions from higher up, citing negative experiences where an employee “*had been waiting for a decision that actually worsened the situation*” (Utility F, appendix 3). While this can be effective for localized issues, it might also contribute to the reluctance to engage other departments or complex reporting chains unless absolutely necessary. The awareness and mitigation efforts in some utilities show recognition of the need to overcome these barriers for specific challenges like operations and IT coordination.

Overall, this preference for flat structures and direct action reflects a culture shaped by practical experience and operational autonomy. While this can support fast and effective local decisions, it may also lead to hesitation in engaging other departments, especially IT, during uncertain or emerging incidents. As seen across the utilities, escalation is not only about procedures but also about trust, culture, and perceived ownership, which shape how IR unfolds in practice.

5.2.3 First actions

Understanding how utilities plan and act during the first 24 hours of a cyber incident is central to examining how IR is organized and executed. This early phase is often the most chaotic and critical, and provides insight into both technical decision-making and organizational coordination under pressure.

The participants were tasked to map out the first actions they would take during the initial 24 hours of a cyber incident. The task was structured along two axes. Vertically, five phases indicated the timeline, and horizontally, a spectrum indicated whether the action was of a technical or organizational nature.

What is included in the matrix in table 10 is information on when the first internal meeting was planned, the balance between organizational and technical actions, the use and timing of islanding, the specific first and last actions taken, the phase when communication was initiated, and which external stakeholders were involved.

Utility	First meeting	Organizational/technical balance	First action in phase 1	Initial response actions	Final response actions	When communication began	External stakeholders involved
A	Phase 1	$\frac{13 \text{ organizational}}{6 \text{ technical}}$ – primarily org	Islanding	Islanding, access to system cut, and start logging	Inform externally, normal operations, and evaluation	Phase 1 (internal), phase 4 (external)	SektorCERT, IR supplier, and insurance
B	Phase 1	$\frac{7 \text{ organizational}}{9 \text{ technical}}$ – more technical	Islanding	Islanding, emergency meeting	Forensics, SektorCERT	Phase 2 (internal), phase 4 (external)	SektorCERT, possibly affected collaborators
C	Phase 2	$\frac{10 \text{ organizational}}{2 \text{ technical}}$ – primarily org	Islanding	Islanding, create an overview	Reporting, crisis staff	Phase 3 (internal and external if necessary)	Board of directors
D	Phase 2	$\frac{10 \text{ organizational}}{9 \text{ technical}}$ – evenly distributed	Islanding	Islandings, pull the chord but don't turn off, and start logging	Find vulnerability, final report of incident	Phase 3 (internal)	IT supplier, OT supplier, external consultants, and CFCS (reporting)
E	Phase 1	$\frac{9 \text{ organizational}}{9 \text{ technical}}$ – evenly distributed	Islanding	Islanding, inform stakeholders, and gather relevant information about the incident	Re-establishment of operations, info to consumers, and external communication	Phase 1 (internal), phase 5 (external)	CFCS, authorities, municipality, and customers
F	Phase 4	$\frac{10 \text{ organizational}}{8 \text{ technical}}$ – more org	Islanding	Create overview, and run islanding on OT	Evaluate and ensure that incident is resolved (takes more than 24h)	Phase 3 (internal), phase 4 (external)	IT supplier, board of directors
G	Phase 1	Not applicable	Not applicable	Create an overview, find contingency plans, and call for meeting	What can be recreated?	Phase 1 (internal), phase 4 (external)	Municipality, mayor, municipality clerk, OT supplier, customers, and IT supplier
H	Phase 2	$\frac{6 \text{ organizational}}{5 \text{ technical}}$ – evenly distributed	Islanding	Islanding, contact: insurance, board, external IT, and external compliance	Normal operations and report the incident	Phase 2 (not specified)	IT supplier, compliance supplier, board of directors, and insurance
I	Phase 1	$\frac{11 \text{ organizational}}{12 \text{ technical}}$ – evenly distributed	Islanding	Islanding, stop the accident, establish crisis team, activate action cards, and start log	Report the incident, plan for getting back to normal operations	Phase 3 (internal)	SektorCERT, authorities, IT supplier, and OT supplier

Table 10: First actions of participating utilities

First phase of IR

The first technical action planned by most companies was the activation of islanding and similar isolation measures. Islanding refers to the deliberate disconnection of OT systems from external networks to prevent the spread of, for example, a cyberattack and maintain core functions under manual control. Islanding, disconnecting systems, or pulling network cables were explicitly mentioned as a first action in the vast majority of the utilities (Utilities A, B, C, D, E, F, H, I). This priority was confirmed by an employee stating, *“Isolating OT from the network is step one”* (Utility F, appendix 3). Similarly, another employee was quick to add the first action to the whiteboard, stating *“I think there are others who have it too – go offline”* (Utility D, appendix 3). The rationale behind this initial action was explained by a participant stating that *“I want to stop the accident first. We’ll start by shutting down the network access. Now we know they’re in there, so we want to get them out again”* (Utility B, appendix 3). The importance of this first action was further emphasized in the prioritization of systems, as one technical employee responded to another employee placing firewall in the top left corner of the important systems matrix, *“I don’t completely agree with that. We can go islanding”* (Utility B, appendix 3). This widespread first action demonstrates that isolating critical OT systems from external networks is a widely recognized and immediate priority, as it allows the utilities to continue providing their essential service of supplying water under manual control, while containing the threat and protecting the core systems. Consequently, this indicates a shared understanding across the sector regarding the necessity of immediate containment as a foundational first step in Phase 1.

Beyond islanding, companies also showed awareness of the need for evidence preservation and initial documentation during the first phase. Actions related to logging or contacting compliance suppliers were mentioned explicitly in four cases (Utility A, D, H, I). The reasoning to do was based on compliance requirements, as noted by actions such as *“create an incident report”* (Utility D, appendix 2), getting explicitly put on the whiteboard. For some utilities, this was an established part of the IR process as stated by one employee *“Logging is relatively clearly described in the contingency plan, both what should be logged, who does the logging, and who is responsible”* (Utility I, appendix 3). While not as universally planned as islanding, the inclusion of these actions indicates a recognition by some that the initial phase is not just about stopping the attack but also about gathering information crucial for understanding the incident, recovery, and potential legal or insurance processes.

However, this was not always a shared understanding, as we found a lack of practical clarity around logging procedures and responsibility in other utilities. Uncertainty about logging was evident as one employee questioned, *“Sorry if this is a stupid question... but regarding this logging — what exactly are we logging? On what? Is it manual?”* (Utility D, appendix 3) questioning how it was accomplished in practice. Similarly, in

another utility, uncertainty around who had this responsibility was noted directly on the post It stating *“Start logbook? (us or IR supplier?)”* (Utility A, appendix 2). Adding to this, different types of logbooks became evident in the discussion as one employee questioned the responsibility, asking *” I wrote down ‘start a logbook,’ but then I asked if that is something the IR provider actually does?”* (Utility A, appendix 3) to which a colleague pointed out that there can be a difference between logging incidents and technical system logs *“There’s a difference — you’re talking about incident logging. What we have here is probably system files.”* (Utility A, appendix 3). Still, some had clear roles that even included backup personnel *“I start a logbook — it’s actually described in our contingency plan, and we can call on someone from your team to help with that if needed”* (Utility F, appendix 3). These examples highlight inconsistencies in the clarity of procedures, the tools or methods for logging, and the roles assigned for this task. Even where plans exist, practical implementation details and ownership can be unclear, especially when external partners are involved. This consistency of isolation suggests that, despite organizational differences, many utilities begin IR with similar technical priorities, providing a foundation for how response efforts are structured and executed across the sector.

Meetings during a cyber incident

Initiating an internal meeting early in the IR was a widely planned organizational action following Islanding. With various names and slightly different focuses like calling for an emergency meeting, assembling relevant staff, informing stakeholders or creating an overview, the importance of organizationally hosting an initial meeting was mentioned as a planned first action or in most utilities (Utility A, B, C, D, E, G, H, I). These meetings were typically placed in phases one or two. This was underscored by a participant urging *“you have to meet immediately. You have to drop everything else you’re doing”* (Utility D, appendix 3). This high frequency indicates that utilities recognize the critical need for immediate team assembly and coordination to assess the situation, assign tasks, and begin managing the response in a structured manner after the initial technical isolation.

Beyond the initial gathering, there was a general desire for continuous coordination sessions with multiple follow-up meetings. The rationale for continuous meetings was articulated by an employee who believed that within the first 24 hours *“you have to meet again, like, once the first actions have been carried out and there’s a status update (...) And then you go out and do those actions and meet again”* (Utility D, appendix 3). This indicates a clear understanding that initial actions often generate further tasks, requiring prompt and continuous coordination to maintain momentum and ensure effective incident management.

When discussing these early meetings, the need for a physical meeting place was highlighted. These meetings were often discussed as explicitly offline events requiring a

specific physical place, and the importance of closeness was mentioned by an employee stating that these meetings are “*physical and it’s face to face*” (Utility A, appendix 3). Similarly, discussions around securing a physical meeting location occurred in other utilities. Some were clear in the location stating that “*in terms of a physical meeting place — it would be here*” (Utility C, appendix 3) referring to the physical branch and conference room in which the workshop was hosted as they had both IT, operations and administration close by supported by the notion that “*It wouldn’t take two seconds to cancel all existing bookings in a conference room and reserve It.*” (Utility C, appendix 3). Others had multiple sites, demonstrating that their contingency plan defined “*three different meeting locations defined, exactly because, if this location is down, then we have alternatives*” (Utility F, appendix 3). However, we also found practical gaps. Despite the recognized need for a location, some utilities had not yet formally selected a location. “*Right now, we haven’t actually designated a crisis conference room yet*” (Utility A, appendix 3) said one employee with a colleague jokingly referring to the place as “*the crisis bunker*” (Utility A, appendix 3). Overall, while establishing a physical meeting place is generally seen as important for these meetings, some utilities still lack a formally designated location.

However, despite the recognized need for coordination, we observed a recurring perspective among operational staff, where the argument came up that more meetings meant more people had to agree, potentially taking unnecessary time from solving the problem. This viewpoint was clear in Utility F, where an OT specialist described a past incident where waiting for a decision delayed the response, making things worse. He felt, “*It’s really important that the people out there are empowered to act and just say, ‘I’m doing this.’ We can deal with the communication or approvals from one or two people afterwards, the point is something has been done*” (Utility F, appendix 3). This critique of delay extended into a critique of blindly following contingency plans, which he felt could cause paralysis stating, “*If you follow the plan slavishly, you’re just sitting there reading*” (Utility F, appendix 3) and described how this could produce inaction, recounting that he experienced that he “*had to wait for someone to approve the next step, so we just stood around*” (Utility F, appendix 3). Similarly, a resistance towards meetings was brought forward by an OT specialist, highlighting the tension between meetings and executing critical technical aspects of the IR “*then you [administrative personnel] can have crisis meetings, and we can get peace to work*” (Utility B, appendix 3). These statements reveal a frustration among operational employees with organizational procedures like meetings that slow down the more technical aspects of response efforts. It reflects a practical, hands-on mindset common among technical staff, who often prioritize immediate containment over formal process. For them, readiness means not just planning and collectively meeting up to solve it, but being trusted to act without waiting for top-down approval. This contrasts with the more process-oriented approach favored by administrative staff in our data, who often emphasize coordination and communication as essential

first steps. This tendency was however not shared in all utilities and as one operational employee stated that meetings did not necessarily complicate their work on the technical side, “*I don’t think there are any obstacles on the contrary, really, it’s more of a partnership between organizational and technical*” (Utility I, appendix 3). The variation in meeting frequency and attitudes toward coordination highlights different organizational approaches to managing the early stages of a cyber incident. These findings illustrate that utilities must balance technical response with organizational coordination when handling cyber incidents.

Timing of contact internally & externally

Within the first actions of the IR exercises, we examined the extent to which actions included internal and external involvement. Here, we found patterns in the external actors that were becoming involved within the first 24 hours of an incident.

A priority for early internal communication was observed in several utilities, starting in Phase two (Utilities A, E, and G). an example was the action “*Communicate the problem to the company (to create an understanding and space to work)*” (Utility A, appendix 2). An employee from another utility nuanced this need explaining that establishing internal calm was important, although immediate communication to all employees was not always deemed necessary “*It depends on how much the issue affects normal operations, not all communication is necessary for everyone.*” (Utility B, appendix 3). The structure of internal communication was also considered, with one utility outlining a hierarchical flow “*First inform the water department, then managers, and then the rest of the staff.*” (Utility A, appendix 3). This focus on early internal information aimed to quickly align response efforts and manage the internal impact of the incident. In contrast to the early internal focus, external communication was typically planned for later phases across most utilities, predominantly occurring from Phase three onwards (Utility A, B, E, F, G). Utility B placed internal communication in phase two and placed external communication reluctantly in phase four “*Possibly inform customers/partners*” (Utility B, appendix 2) and phase five “*Contact SektorCERT*” (Utility B, appendix 2). They underlined this delayed external communication, declaring that when they had an overview of the situation, they would inform the public, for example by SMS or on their website: “*When we know roughly what it is, we send something out, maybe an SMS or a website update.*” (Utility B, appendix 3). The perceived necessity to inform the consumers was evident, even if the exact steps were sometimes unclear, as one participant jokingly suggested “*If needed, you could drive around with a loudspeaker.*” (Utility B, appendix 3).

We wanted to find out who, outside the organizations, were contacted within the first 24 hours, especially IR partners and authorities. What we found was that a group of external organizations could support with technical expertise. Several utilities planned to contact IT suppliers (Utility A, D, F, G, H, I), OT suppliers (Utility D, G, I), and

compliance suppliers (Utility H), while insurance was two utilities (Utility A, H). Cybersecurity support was also frequently included, with SektorCERT (Utility A, B, I), and external consultants like IR Supplier planned by (Utility A, D). The involvement of these technical partners underscores the recognition that addressing complex cyber incidents often requires external specialized knowledge beyond in-house capabilities.

We also observed that participants often would contact authorities with an intent beyond just regulatory reporting. This included national bodies like CFCS (Utility D, E), as well as local municipality representatives from the (Utility E, G), a direct connection to the mayor (Utility G), and the municipality clerk (Utility G). Furthermore, the utilities board of directors, which is inherently political for the municipality owned utilities, was planned for involvement by three utilities (Utility C, F, H).

While contacting authorities was often perceived as a regulatory obligation, “*then there may be a fine because we have not fulfilled our obligation to inform the supervisory authority*” (Utility E, appendix 3), some utilities also viewed those authorities as potential communicative partners with great communication channels. One utility planned to “*Inform regulator*” (Utility E, appendix 2) and “*Contact authorities*” (Utility E, appendix 2) in Phases three and four, with the explicit purpose of leveraging their channels stating “*We contact the regulator, and they spread it out through their channels*” (Utility E, appendix 3).

A few utilities would contact external contacts related to legal aspects. Insurance contact was explicitly mentioned by two utilities (Utility A, H). This indicates an awareness of the potential costs and liabilities associated with cyber incidents and the need to involve insurers early in the process.

Organizational vs. technical action

A pattern emerged regarding the distribution of technical versus organizational actions at the utilities.

For the purposes of this analysis, technical actions refer to measures aimed at directly interacting with or modifying IT and OT systems, like isolating networks or shutting down access, while organizational actions encompass coordination, documentation, communication, or decision-making processes. The judgment of placing the actions into these two categories was made by the participants.

We observed that many utilities achieved a balanced amount of organizational and technical actions, with some outliers as well. The majority of utilities showed a balance between technical and organizational responses. This balance was often manifested either by having an exactly equal number of actions (Utility E) or by having a slight leaning, typically with one or two more organizational actions than technical ones (Utility B, D, F, H, I). This balanced approach was prevalent across several utilities. For instance, Utility H’s plan outlined a nearly even distribution, with six organizational and five technical

actions. This utility tended to execute organizational actions in the initial phases of their response, while technical actions were more evenly spread across the five phases of their process (Utility H, appendix 2). Similarly, Utility D exhibited a balanced distribution, listing ten technical and nine organizational actions. Their initial steps underscored this integrated approach, encompassing both technical containment measures like *"pull the cable"* (Utility D, appendix 2) and organizational tasks such as *"start logbook"* (Utility D, appendix 2). Utility E further exemplified this balance with an exactly equal split of nine technical and nine organizational actions. Their early actions combined technical isolation efforts with organizational activities like *"Inform relevant stakeholders"* (Utility E, appendix 2) and *"gathering relevant info about the incident and create an overview"* (Utility E, appendix 2). This integrated and diverse set of initial actions suggests a broad perspective on IR, acknowledging that effective handling involves the wider organization and necessitates the parallel execution of technical work and organizational coordination.

However, this pattern of balance was not universal, and some utilities deviated significantly, either by skewing heavily towards organizational action or by not subscribing to the premises of the exercise. Utility A showed a notable bias towards organizational actions, listing 13 organizational actions compared to just six technical ones. However, their immediate first steps were still focused on technical containment methods such as *"Islanding"* (Utility A, appendix 2) and *"Stop the bleeding (access to systems is cut/severed)"* (Utility A, appendix 2). Similarly, utility C demonstrated a strong initial technical bias in their plan, outlining 10 technical actions but only two organizational ones among their early phases. Utility G presented a different approach to the exercise. Rather than distributing actions along a technical-organizational axis, the CEO instructed the participants to write down their own actions stating, *"So the way to do it is really writing down what your own actions are. I write down what I do and you do it accordingly"* (Utility G, appendix 3). Their planning then consisted of documenting each individual's actions and mapping them to response phases, bypassing the technical-organizational framework entirely (Utility G, appendix 2).

Overall, we found technical actions to be similar across the utilities, while the organizational ones were more diverse. Our observations suggest that technical actions, such as the relatively uniform response of islanding, appear clearer and more standardized for organizations. In contrast, the organizational actions are notably more varied, likely because they lack the same clear structure and established processes as their technical counterparts. It is important to note that these classifications are based purely on the actions documented in the exercise and serve as a proxy because the level of detail in the actions varied from simple phrasings to detailed descriptions.

The distribution of organizational and technical actions shows how utilities generally approach response as an organizational effort. These similarities in the technical actions and variety in the organizational ones help us understand the degree to which IR is integrated in the utilities.

What is possible within 24 hours?

Looking closer at the actions utilities expected towards the end of the first 24 hours, mainly in Phase four and Phase five, reveals their understanding of what is realistically achievable shortly after a cyberattack and how they perceive the ending of the critical first 24 hours of the response phase.

Many utilities anticipated being engaged in technical stabilization during this timeframe. For instance, several utilities placed actions like "*Re-establishing normal operations from backup*" (Utility F, appendix 2), "*System recovery*" (Utility C, appendix 2), or "*Getting back to normal operation if possible*" (Utility G, appendix 2) towards the very end of the 24-hour window. This focus indicates a primary goal of mitigating immediate technical damage and restoring essential services as quickly as possible, moving from initial containment towards functional recovery.

Organizationally, many utilities planned to initiate evaluation and documentation tasks late in the 24 hours. Actions such as "*Evaluation*" (Utility A, appendix 2), "*Incident report finalization*" (Utility D, appendix 2), and "*Document what can be recovered*" (Utility G, appendix 2) suggest that utilities expect to begin the formal process of closing the incident relatively early. This planning was evident in the utilities, whose actions in phase five included elements like reporting or evaluation (Utility A, C, D, F, H, I). This highlights the recognition that an effective IR involves not just technical fixes but also capturing lessons learned and formally recording the event and its impact. Some also saw external communication as a crucial final step within the 24-hour period. One utility included the actions "*Information to customers (if relevant)*" (Utility E, appendix 2) and "*Communication with authorities*" (Utility E, appendix 2) in the last two phases. Similarly, another utility mentioned "*SektorCERT contact*" (Utility B, appendix 2) and "*Customer information if needed*" (Utility B, appendix 2) towards the end.

However, the exercise also revealed how some utilities had a pragmatic understanding of what is possible within the first 24 hours. For instance, one utility included post-its like "*Delete everything*" (Utility F, appendix 2) and "*Ensure everything is OK*" (Utility F, appendix 2) towards the end of their timeline. This indicates that for some, the focus is simply on ensuring systems are clean, safe, and stable, rather than necessarily achieving complete recovery or finalizing all organizational processes immediately. It may reflect a more realistic acknowledgment that the first 24 hours are primarily for damage control and stabilization.

Overall, most utilities see the first phases as dedicated to technical damage control and organizational stabilization, with deeper analysis, rebuilding, and communicating as follow-up actions. Thereby, we find a tendency that some utilities may treat the incident as initially requiring technical actions with communicative and formal procedures following. The way utilities plan their final actions within the first 24 hours reflects how they define the scope of initial response versus long-term recovery. This helps us

understand the practical limits of response execution and how utilities set priorities.

5.2.4 Communication

Communication is a key part of IR as it shapes how information is shared within the organization and with external stakeholders. Understanding how utilities plan and carry out communication helps us reveal how IR is coordinated and managed. During the workshops, the companies created an overview of how they would communicate during a cyber incident. They were asked to decide who should be informed, what those people should know, and which overall channels they would use. The matrix in table 11 below covers the five main communication groups found in our data, which were *internal staff*, *top management*, *customers*, *media*, and *authorities*. For each group, the type and level of information to be shared are summarized. The matrix also includes the overall preferred communication channels.

Utility	Internal	Top management	Customers	Media	Authorities	Channels
A	Water staff receive detailed information about the situation and the action plan. Other staff receive a Q&A.	Informed that something is going on, but no details are provided.	Informed only on a need-to-know basis.	Direct line to local newspaper: informed on a need-to-know basis.	Authorities receive a report of the incident and technical insights via CFCS.	1. Phone 2. Email 3. Social media and SMS
B	Informed by email about the incident. Brought in on the action plan after it is developed.	Receive detailed information focused on potential consequences and timeline.	Informed about how the disturbance will affect them, with ongoing short updates.	Receive limited information until the incident is resolved.	Not mentioned.	Phone, SMS, and website (no set priority).
C	Informed about irregularities in the affected area.	Receive a short message about the irregular situation.	Informed only if relevant.	Informed only if relevant.	Informed only if relevant.	No set priority; depends on incident specifics.
D	Informed about tasks, who should come to work, and what needs to be prioritized.	Informed about what happened, current status, and economic consequences.	Informed that it is a cyberattack and referred to the communication department.	Are contacted and involved.	Contacted and involved	1. Email and phone 2. Website 3. Radio/Eboks
E	Provided with a description of the incident, consequences, status, who is affected, and available options.	Not mentioned.	Given a short description of the incident and who is involved.	Given a short description of the incident and who is involved.	Informed of incident details, consequences, affected areas, and technical information.	1. Website, email, SMS 2. RadioABC, TV2 OJ, newspaper 3. Social media
F	Shared only with the communication department: status, scope of attack, and next steps.	Informed of status, scope of the attack, and next planned steps.	Communication depends on the situation.	Not mentioned.	Response depends on the situation; the municipality is given status and technical information.	1. SMS 2. Nordjyske/TV2 Nord
G	Informed on a need-to-know basis: only trusted employees receive a threat summary in strict confidence.	Receive a confidential summary of the threat/incident.	Not mentioned.	Not mentioned.	City manager receives a confidential summary of the threat/incident.	1. Verbal updates with crisis staff, possibly by phone
H	Not mentioned.	Informed of current findings, impact assessment, and completed actions.	Informed to the extent they are affected.	Not mentioned.	Informed via 24-hour and 72-hour reports.	1. Email 2. Phone 3. In-person contact
I	Told that it is an emergency being handled internally: no media contact allowed.	Informed that it is an incident being handled; more information to follow.	Not mentioned.	Not mentioned.	Not mentioned.	1. Phone 2. Email/intranet

Table 11: Communication strategies by stakeholder and preferred channel

Most utilities acknowledged the importance of internal communication, but the level of planning varied. Two utilities (Utility A, D) used structured approaches to internal communication such as “*who has to work*” (Utility D, appendix 2), staff instructions, or “*Q&A*” (Utility A, appendix 2). In contrast, others provided only vague or situational messages such as “*abnormal operational situation*” (Utility C, appendix 2) or “*Internal information is sent via email, and information is possibly passed on at an extraordinary meeting*” (Utility B, appendix 2) thereby not sharing details unless needed. The importance of involving internal personnel was emphasized by one participant noting that non-technical staff might have to step in during an incident, “*Employees should know what we can and cannot do right now. Sometimes even an administration worker like [anonymized name] may need to go press a button.*” (Utility D, appendix 3). This highlights that during a crisis, broad internal awareness is crucial. One utility broke this pattern as they did not mention internal communication as a group in their plan (Utility H, appendix 3). This indicates that most utilities see internal communication as important. However, a divide still exists between communication models where some utilities aim to actively involve staff, while others take a more passive, need-to-know approach.

These differences highlight varying levels of internal coordination and staff involvement. They give insight into how each utility organizes its internal response and communication to the rest of the organization during an incident.

Communication with top management was treated differently across cases. Some companies prioritized informing the management with detailed information about the status, consequences, and the estimated time for recovery in detail (Utility B, D, F, G, H). In other utilities, communication to management was less detailed, only describing the area under impact (Utility A, C, I). This shows that some organizations view management as part of the crisis response, while others see them more as an audience to be informed later in the process.

Customer communication was usually handled with caution. Most utilities wanted to inform customers following the principle of need to know and only if it directly impacted them (Utility A, B, C, E, F, H, I). Some utilities clearly stated that information should focus on how the incident affects the customers, not on what exactly happened (Utility B, H). Although utility I did not specifically mention contact with customers in the exercise, they later discussed why they would not include them, “*There’s no reason to communicate to them [the customers] if they’re not affected, because it will overwhelm us. I mean, the organization will simply be brought to its knees*” (Utility I, appendix 3).

In several cases, SMS systems or simple website updates were mentioned as the preferred method of communication with customers. A participant stated “*for citizens our media is website or it is SMS*” (Utility D, appendix 3). Multiple utilities mentioned the software *Blue Idea*, which allows them to send out SMS’s to their customers (Utility A, B, D, E, F, G, H, I, appendix 3).

The responses reveal a cautious approach to customer communication, where utilities

prioritize control over messaging but lack strategic clarity. Without clear plans, even effective channels like SMS or websites may fall short in a crisis.

Media communication was mentioned by some utilities (Utility A, B, C, D, E), and was similar to contacting customers based on a need-to-know approach. One utility pointed out why careful media communication is important, referencing a past experience where a small controlled explosion when cleaning a sludge tank to shake the walls slightly. Here, a participant stated *“One time, the local newspaper wrongly reported that the utility was about to be exploded. We were flooded with calls. A small mistake in information can cause huge panic”* (Utility B, appendix 3).

This fear was shared by other utilities, which mentioned risking losing control of the narrative and that a small incident could lead to considerable reputational implications. Utility A had a plan to contact the local newspaper themselves and *“talk to them and say if you hear anything, don’t publish it until you check with us first.”* (Utility A, appendix 3). This reflects a broader strategy among utilities to engage with the media selectively and cautiously, offering only essential information in order to minimize the risk of miscommunication. The goal is not only to protect public trust but also to maintain control over how incidents are perceived externally.

Utilities demonstrated varied approaches to communicating with authorities during a cyber incident. Some planned for active and structured participation, giving the authorities details about the situation, consequences, status, and even technical insights for entities like CFCS or the municipality (Utility A, E, F, H). This reflects an understanding of the authorities’ need for information for coordination and reporting. In contrast, other utilities were more hesitant, stating communication would occur *“only if relevant”* (Utility C, appendix 2) or did not explicitly mention authorities in their initial plans (Utility B), while Utility G planned confidential summaries for the municipality clerk (Utility G). This variation possibly stems from differing perceptions of the immediate role of authorities in the technical response, regulatory requirements, or established relationships. The nature of the information shared also varied. A participant noted the municipality only needed to know *“when we are back up again”* (Utility E, appendix 3), emphasizing a focus on status and impact. Some utilities explicitly planned to share technical details (Utility A, G). Furthermore, the timing of communication was seen as critical. One participant cautioned, *“You can’t just cry wolf without knowing. You have to find out what’s really happening before communicating”* (Utility F, appendix 3), underscoring the need for verified information before engaging authorities. Overall, the utilities’ approaches to communicating with authorities during an incident span from detailed technical briefings to minimal status updates.

We observed that utilities showed varied approaches in their choice of communication channels during a cyber incident, largely influenced by the intended audiences. Direct channels like phone calls were mentioned by some utilities (Utility A, B, D, G, H, I) together with emails (Utility A, D, H, I), which were generally placed as primary methods,

particularly for internal communication and rapid coordination among crisis staff. This highlights their perceived value for handover specific details and coordinating immediate actions privately. In parallel wider-reach channels such as SMS messages via *Blue idea* (Utility A, B, E, F), website updates (Utility B, D, E), social media (Utility A, E) and traditional media like radio or local news outlets (Utility D, E, F) were primarily intended for external communication. These channels are crucial for broadcasting timely alerts, status updates, and public safety information to customers, the media, or the general public. This shows that utilities have different go-to channels for internal and external communication, which depend on whether the messaging is direct and personal or for a broader audience.

The utilities all saw communication as important during a cyber incident, but they planned and handled it in different ways. We also saw how they used different channels depending on who they were addressing. Some would give clear instructions to their staff, others would only give basic updates. Most were careful about what to tell customers and the media to avoid panic or confusion. How these differences may play out in practice may also have something to do with how the roles and responsibilities are distributed, which will be examined in the next section.

5.2.5 Roles & responsibilities

Understanding who holds which roles and responsibilities during a cyber incident is central to understanding how IR is organized and executed.

Throughout the workshops, participants were tasked with designing an IR team. The overall roles had the themes of IT, Economy, communication, operations, compliance, lead, and other (see table 12). Some roles were universally prioritized or deprioritized, while others revealed differences across utilities. These choices reflected not only practical considerations but also varying assumptions about authority, expertise, and responsibility during a crisis. The exercise offered a look into how different utilities organize their response capabilities and how the people around the table can shape the execution of the response.

Utility	Number of People Involved	Economy	Communication	Lead	IT	Operations	Compliance	Others
A	9	Business Director	Head of Communication + Head of Customer Service	Head of IT	IT Employee	Head of Water	Compliance Responsible	Quality Responsible + CEO
B	6	CFO	Head of Communication	Head of IT + IT Employee	Head of IT + IT Employee	Head of Operations + Head of Wastewater	Head of IT + IT Employee + Head of Communication	None
C	8 (External IT and Management)	CEO + CFO + Operations (possibly)	Management + Communication employee	External IT	External IT	Head of Operations + Head of Area Affected	Compliance	None
D	7 (Management)	CFO	Head of Communication	CISO	IT-Employee	Head of Operations	CISO + Compliance Responsible	Management
E	8	CFO	Head of Communication	Head of Water Operations	Head of IT	Head of Production	CISO + Head of Legal	Head of Utilities
F	6	Head of Operations + Head of Water and wastewater	Head of Water and Wastewater	Head of Operation	CISO + Head of IT	Head of Operations + Team Leader On Operation and Control	CISO	Municipality
G	6	CFO	CEO + Water Operations	CEO	Water Operations/IT Responsible	Operational employee	Head of Development	Head of Development
H	8	CFO	Head of Communication	CEO + Head of Administration	Head of IT	Head of Operations	External Compliance Supplier	External IT
I	9 (IT Supplier, SektorCERT, and OT Supplier)	CFO	Head of Communication	Head of IT	IT Employee	Head of Operations + Head of Water Operations	Unknown	IT Supplier + SektorCERT,+ OT Supplier

Table 12: Incident Response team composition

The total number of people formally involved in the core IR teams showed limited variation across utilities. We generally found the number of people listed to vary only slightly, ranging from six (Utility B, F, G) to nine people (Utility A, I). While the lists primarily covered named roles or individuals, some teams included broader terms like *Management* (Utility C, D) or *External IT* (Utility C, I), which may include multiple people. However, this was not clearly defined, We counted such roles as a single person.

Economic responsibility

The assignment of economic responsibility during an incident was the first area examined. While the typical responsibility for economic fallout due to incidents is delegated to senior management roles like CFO or CEO (Utility A, B, C, D, E, G, H, I) in all but a single utility, active financial management during the crisis itself is not a primary focus and is sometimes viewed skeptically. This was expressed by a CFO who stated *“I have a hard time seeing that as a top priority, even though I’m the CFO [...] What matters is solving the problem, and what it ends up costing is less important”* (Utility D, appendix 3) suggesting that financial oversight is not seen as the main priority during IR, even for a CFO.

This perceived lower priority for active financial management during the crisis stems from a strong belief that resolving the technical problem takes precedence over cost considerations in the initial phases of the incident. Expressed by a participant *“It’s not like we’d say, ‘Well, we don’t have the budget for that, so we won’t do anything’”* (Utility D, appendix 3). This perspective was so prevalent that when asked about financial activity, we were met with surprise that financial stakeholders would even be considered part of the response team. A CEO underscored this view regarding potential downtime, stating, *“Downtime of 24 hours. I think it’s marginal what it costs us”* (Utility C, appendix 3) as immediate costs were perceived as relatively minor.

Communicative responsibility

This low emphasis on the financial concerns meant that some utilities expressed concern that the involvement of financial stakeholders could even hinder the essential operational recovery effort. As one technical participant said about immediate action *“first do first-aid, it should not wait too long for all sorts of other people who have to come over.”* (Utility C, appendix 3). While the costs of internal disruption were largely downplayed, a minor financial concern was noted, specifically tied to external expenditure, such as bringing in outside help. A CEO clarified how a financial impact eventually might be significant when stating *“That’s only when we have to bring in specialists.”* (Utility C, appendix 3). This shows that most utilities do not see financial management as part of the core response and helps explain how their response teams are organized and what

they prioritize during an incident.

Communication roles are generally not highly prioritized or viewed as having independent authority within utilities' IR teams. Communication roles were most commonly handled by the head of Communication (Utility A, B, C, D, E, H, F), sometimes in combination with other departments like customer service (Utility A) or management (Utility C, G). We also saw some utilities incorporate the head of operations (Utility F, G) for this responsibility.

While most utilities identified a head of Communication or similar as responsible, this person was often described as someone who *"must be fed by others"* (Utility B, appendix 3), with overall authority perceived as residing higher up, as in the comment *"It will be the management that will pull the strings"* (Utility C, appendix 3). This indicates that the communication function is frequently seen as secondary to the immediate technical and operational response, lacking impact within the crisis command structure. Furthermore, communication roles were seen as primarily handling external-facing support functions, which tends to create a one-way information flow. One employee explained this view of communications, stating *"It must be the communications department that gets in touch with externals"* (Utility F, appendix 3). This perspective views communication staff as receiving information from technical teams rather than actively participating in the core IR processes where that information is generated and analyzed. This finding suggests that communication is often seen as a support function, not as part of the main response.

Lead

Analyzing the role of those who held the overall coordinating responsibility for the incident revealed a notable variation across utilities. While some assigned leadership from IT or a CISO (Utility A, B, D, I), the responsibility is also held by operative leadership (Utility E, F, H) or by the CEO (Utility G). Additionally, one utility took a different approach by having an external lead in the form of their IT supplier (Utility C).

Despite IT often taking a prominent role or even the lead, tension and uncertainty about overall coordinating responsibility can sometimes arise, particularly concerning the boundary with operations. While many utilities could easily identify their IR lead, others experienced internal confusion about authority. This tension was illustrated when a head of operations was initially named as lead, prompting the head of IT to immediately state *"On the IT side, it's me"* (Utility F, appendix 3). This triggered further discussion about operational boundaries during incidents, *"IT and OT are two different things. (...) for OT There is a contingency plan, and you should not confuse it with IT. It must be separated"* (Utility F, appendix 3). Unlike conventional emergencies, where utilities typically have established contingency plans with clear structures often managed under operations, cybersecurity incidents require expertise and coordination across these traditionally separated technical and operational domains. Overall, managing incidents like

this needs different types of knowledge and coordination between multiple departments, so no one universal role was identified.

IT & operational responsibility

We found clear responsibilities of both IT and operations across the utilities, with minimal organizational variation. IT responsibility was given to personnel consisting of head of it, IT employee or the CISO across the majority of utilities (Utility A, B, D, E, F, H, I) with only slight variation as one had external IT (Utility C) and one had an internal employee coordinating with their IT supplier (Utility G). Operational responsibilities during the cyber incident were even more unison as they were all delegated to roles in the operational management. One employee reflected on these two areas stating, “*What is more important, OT or IT?*” (Utility D, appendix 3) emphasizing that without OT “*then we have the challenge of delivery*” (Utility D, appendix 3) while with an IT breakdown could give “*problems even with sending an invoice*” (Utility D, appendix 3). This consistency in responsibility shows clear operational boundaries for the day-to-day management of their technical systems.

Compliance responsibility

The delegation of compliance responsibilities varied significantly across utilities, with differences in both structure and integration into IR processes. Some utilities had dedicated compliance or legal personnel internally (Utility A, C, D, E) or externally (Utility H) others placed responsibility on top of existing roles (Utility B, F, G). A single utility did not know who had the compliance responsibility and left it unanswered (Utility I).

The presence of a dedicated compliance responsible had a notable impact on how the utilities handled regulatory requirements. A compliance responsible emphasized documentation during the response, stating, “*always have it written down on a piece of paper, because that is also the documentation you have to report.*” (Utility D, appendix 3). They also viewed regulatory reporting not as a single event but as an ongoing activity “*When we report, we have 24 hours, so the thing about saying now we have reached this far in the process, and then we can always update*” (Utility D, appendix 3). This proactive approach contrasted sharply with utilities placing the responsibility on top of existing roles, where reporting was typically treated as a separate administrative task to be completed after the technical handling of the incident was largely concluded. Overall, this indicates that the placement of compliance responsibility is critical for fostering proactive integration of regulatory requirements into IR rather than treating them as afterthoughts when operations are back to normal.

High ranking stakeholders

Additional personnel involved in the IR team were primarily high-ranking stakeholders who required notification rather than active participation in response activities. When given the opportunity to identify additional individuals beyond our predefined categories, utilities consistently mentioned hierarchically senior figures, including the management (Utility A, D), the overall head of utilities (Utility E), and the municipality being the owner (Utility F).

These stakeholders' roles were characterized as passive recipients of information rather than active participants. As one employee explicitly stated regarding their local municipality. *"They will have no influence on what we do about it when we talk about water. It is you [the IR team] who decide it, but they have to sit at the table"* (Utility F, appendix 3). This arrangement creates a dynamic where senior leadership is consciously involved, yet their input on technical response decisions is deliberately limited. The organizational structure thus maintains a functional separation between operational response teams and higher-ranking stakeholders, allowing technical experts to manage incidents while keeping stakeholders informed.

This section shows that while technical roles like IT and operations are clearly organized, other roles like communication, compliance, and leadership are handled differently across utilities. These differences help shed light on how IR is set up, who takes action, and what utilities see as important during a cyber incident.

5.2.6 Authority involvement

Reporting to authorities as a water utility will most likely be obligatory under the NIS2 regulation. Therefore, how and when utilities engage with official reporting processes gives insight into how they understand their responsibilities and how they prioritize external coordination during an incident. This was the focus in one of the final tasks within the scenario, which was about reporting the incident to the authorities, using a recreation of the official reporting formula. Table 13 shows which authorities they reported to, the type of incident they chose, and whether they needed technical assistance from CFCS

Utility	Who do they report to? (Besides CFCS)	Type of incident registered	Requested need for technical assistance
A	Ministry of Environment and Food	Malicious actions	X
B	The energy agency	Malicious actions	X
C	Ministry of Environment and Food + Danish Health Authority	Malicious actions	X
D	Ministry of Environment and Food	Malicious actions	✓
E	Ministry of Environment and Food	Malicious actions + System failure + Human error	X

Utility	Who do they report to? (Besides CFCS)	Type of incident registered	Requested need for technical
F	Ministry of Environment and Food	Malicious actions	✓
G	Ministry of Environment and Food	Malicious actions	X
H	Ministry of Environment and Food	Malicious actions	X
I	Ministry of Environment and Food	Malicious actions	✓

Table 13: Incident Reporting and Assistance Needs

We found that utilities generally reported the incident similarly, but with notable differences regarding the need for technical assistance from CFCS. The utilities showed consistency when identifying both the authority to report the incident to and the type of incident involved. When filling out the form from CFCS, almost all utilities selected the option where the incident was reported to both the CFCS and the Ministry of Environment and Food, which showed consistency in knowledge about whom to report to. Utility B chose a different option because they interpreted the scenario to possibly affect other areas, which they supplied, rather than a misunderstanding of the general reporting structure. This suggests the form’s options were generally clear for identifying the primary reporting path. We found a similar pattern of agreement regarding the type of incident. All utilities identified the event as “*Malicious actions (cyberattacks, physical attacks, DDoS...)*” (Appendix 2). Although Utility E also identified elements of system failure and human error. This was seen as an addition to, rather than a contradiction of, the main classification as a malicious action. This consistency suggests that Danish water utilities are aligned in their understanding of formal reporting procedures, which reflects a shared foundation in how incidents are reported.

There was a split when choosing whether CFCS would be needed for technical assistance. The utilities showed reluctance amongst them to seek technical assistance from the CFCS during an incident. As one participant stated, “*We communicate first with those who can solve the problem the most. [...] They [CFCS] can’t. They can’t help at all.*” (Utility I, appendix 3). This reluctance manifested in multiple ways. Firstly, when directly asked on the reporting form if they required assistance, a majority (Utility A, B, C, E, G, H) explicitly declined. Secondly, subsequent discussions highlighted widespread skepticism regarding CFCS’s effectiveness in providing practical help. Several utilities reacted with direct laughter “*haha they don’t know what they saying*” (Utility E, appendix 3), suggesting CFCS involvement might be counterproductive and do more harm than good and questioned their impact “*How much can they actually come and help?*” (Utility E, appendix 3). Furthermore, some utilities indicated they rely on alternative support systems, implying CFCS assistance was unnecessary “*if we say no, we can write here that it is because we have [name of an IR provider] and SektorCERT involved*” (Utility A, appendix 3).

Among the utilities that accepted help from CFCS (Utility D, F, I), precautions were taken. One offered a hesitant acceptance “*You can always say yes*” (Utility D, appendix 3). Another utility accepting help, still intended to tightly control CFCS’s involvement to prevent disruption, stating, “*but then I take them by the hand and then make sure that they don’t bother you too much*” (Utility F, appendix 3).

This showed us that alternative technical assistance was preferred rather than technical help by CFCS, as even those who accepted the help generally did not see them as an effective source of technical assistance.

The main concerns for this rejection of CFCS appeared to be a perceived lack of necessary technical expertise and the potential for CFCS involvement to complicate things rather than help the situation. Therefore, while the utilities may comply with reporting requirements to CFCS, there is a clear gap in trust or perceived value regarding receiving support from them.

These findings show that the utilities follow the formal reporting process. However, they do not see CFCS as a helpful partner during incidents. Depending on the incident, this could reveal an important gap between official expectations and how IR is actually carried out in practice, which is a key concern in this study. These gaps between formal structures and practical actions are central to understanding how Danish water utilities respond to real incidents.

5.3 Cross-case meta matrix

To support our cross-case analysis and explore how Danish water utilities organize and execute cyber IR, we developed a meta-matrix inspired by the approach proposed by Miles and Huberman (1994). This matrix allowed us to bring together key findings. Each column reflects a theme from the analysis. The content of each cell therefore reflects the outcome of condensing the thematic matrix for each utility under a specific theme. This structure allowed us to compare overall patterns across utilities while still retaining the specific context of each case and theme.

Utility	Size	System reliance	Escalation	First Actions	Communication	Roles & Responsibilities	Authority involvement
A	Medium utility	Internal and external setup. Critical systems, external.	Long chain. First step: head of operations.	Primarily organizational. 3 externals involved.	Only internal water staff. Everyone else needs to know. CFCS involved	IT leads and the CEO is support. Dedicated compliance role	Reports to Ministry. No technical help needed.
B	Smaller utility	Internal and mixed setup. critical systems, mixed.	Medium chain. First step: head of operations	More technical. 1 external involved + affected collaborators	Informs all staff and customers after initial plans except media	IT lead and no CEO.	Reports to Energy Agency. No technical help needed.
C	Medium utility	Internal setup. critical systems, external.	Short chain. First step: Management.	Primarily organizational. 1 external involved.	Shares limited info, both internally and externally.	External IT leads with many support roles. Dedicated compliance role	Reports to Ministry + Health. No technical help needed.
D	Smaller utility	Very external setup. critical systems, external.	Medium chain. First step: head of operations	Evenly distributed. 4 externals involved.	Communicates actively with staff, customers, media, and authorities.	IT leads and management supports. dedicated compliance role	Reports to Ministry. Technical help requested.
E	Larger utility	Internal and mixed setup. critical systems, internal and mixed.	Long chain. First step: Operational employee.	Evenly distributed. 4 externals involved.	Gives non detailed information to all relevant groups	Operational role leads, and CEO involved.	Reports to Ministry. No technical help needed.
F	Larger utility	Internal setup. critical systems fully internal.	Short chain. First step: Nearest leader.	More organizational. 2 externals involved.	status and scale of attack. Nothing to media.	Operational role leads, IT is responsible for compliance, municipality person in team.	Reports to Ministry. Technical help requested.
G	Smaller utility	Very external setup. Critical systems, external.	Short chain. First step: Operational employee.	Not applicable. 6 externals involved.	Communicates only with selected staff in strict confidence.	CEO leads and helps with communication, IT both operations and IT personnel.	Reports to Ministry. No technical help needed.
H	Smaller utility	Fully external setup. Critical systems, external.	Medium chain. First step: headof operations.	Evenly distributed. 4 externals involved.	Sends short status updates to affected users by SMS; no wider outreach.	CEO and head of administration lead, compliance is external.	Reports to Ministry. No technical help needed.
I	Medium utility	Very Mixed setup. critical systems, mixed.	Medium chain. First step: operational employee.	Evenly distributed. 4 externals involved.	Says the situation is under control but gives no further details. no media.	IT leads, external actors help, compliance role is unclear.	Reports to Ministry. Technical help requested.

Table 14: Cross-Case Meta-Matrix summarizing responses across IR themes

Looking across the full meta-matrix, Miles and Huberman (1994) explain that patterns can become clearer when all themes are viewed side by side. These are not always visible in the individual thematic matrices but stand out when placed next to each other.

A pattern emerges when comparing utility size and system reliance, where larger utilities tend to have greater internal control over their critical systems. Large utilities, such as E and F, have their critical systems internally managed. Simultaneously, when an incident occur these are the only ones where operational personnel takes the lead. In contrast, smaller utilities, such as D, G, and H, rely on external vendors for managing their most critical systems and their IT in general. This suggests that as utility size increases, organizations generally have stronger in-house capacity for handling an incident.

When the management lead the IR process, communication tends to be more controlled. In utility G, H, and E, where the CEO takes the lead, communication is generally narrow in scope. In contrast, in the other utilities where IT or operations take the lead, communication is generally more varied and can be either open or controlled. This indicates that when leadership takes responsibility, communication becomes more controlled, possibly due to the increased focus on reputation and public perception of this role.

When comparing the escalation chain and communication style in the meta-matrix, a pattern emerges. Utilities with short escalation chains, such as C, F, and G, tend to limit communication to internal teams or a narrow circle of staff. For instance, utility G communicates only with selected staff in strict confidence, and utility F shares only the status and scale of the incident internally without involving the media. In contrast, utilities with longer or more layered escalation chains, such as A, D, and E, tend to engage in broader communication efforts. This suggests that a more structured escalation process supports wider communication outreach.

6 Discussion

In this discussion, we interpret our analytical findings through our selected theoretical lenses to understand how cybersecurity IR is practiced in the Danish water sector. We explore what our findings mean in practice, how they hold up against existing literature, to see where they challenge, confirm, or nuance understandings of IR in the water sector. The areas that we will discuss are specifically about the importance of quick isolation practices, the difficulties at the IT-operations intersection, the bridging of existing partnerships and national help, the prioritization of reputation over economy, the often low priority of communication, and the implications of having different roles as part of the IR.

6.1 Quick isolation practices

A key finding from this study is the widespread and intuitive use of islanding as an initial response strategy across Danish water utilities. What makes this practice significant is not only its technical feasibility but the degree to which it is organizationally embedded across utilities. This involves the immediate implementation of islanding procedures applied consistently across the sector without hesitation regarding timing or methodology. Remarkably, even smaller utilities with limited internal staff independently initiated islanding protocols, hereby demonstrating how deeply ingrained this procedure is. This consistency is notable and indicates a high degree of operational readiness in the initial steps of IR throughout the sector.

This consistency in initial response stands in contrast to the broader SME literature. Manzoor et al. (2024) and Asadi et al. (2025) emphasize that SMEs often lack the expertise necessary for effective cybersecurity and act too late. Contrary to these findings, our research reveals that Danish water utilities possess a clear understanding and perceived expertise for managing the initial stages of an incident, as evidenced by the quick and consistent application of islanding procedures throughout the utilities. This suggests that while general challenges may exist for SMEs, the sector-specific contexts of these utilities appear to foster a high degree of readiness in this critical first step of IR.

The effectiveness of islanding in Danish utilities might be closely linked to the roles and experience of the personnel responsible. In all cases, the personnel responsible for initiating islanding had deep operational experience and were already accustomed to handling alarms and contingency plans. Water utilities, especially the operational staff, are working in alert-based environments and are consequently trained and experienced in reacting quickly to system anomalies. This stands in contrast to other sectors and departments where routine work is more planning-oriented and less reactive. Drawing on Kocksch and Elgaard Jensen's (2023) overall argument that cybersecurity practices are shaped by the role taking responsibility, our findings expand on this by showing that operational roles, even without formal cybersecurity training, can be more naturally

aligned with rapid IR because of their day-to-day exposure to disruptions and emergency routines.

However, this heavy reliance on operational staff and their instinct for rapid, independent technical action presents potential trade-offs in later incident phases. Our findings indicate a clash between this immediate, technical focus and broader organizational coordination. Several participants, particularly from operations, expressed frustration with formal coordination procedures such as meetings and escalation protocols, often viewing them as bureaucratic hurdles that hinder their technical work. While this preference for quickness is effective for initial isolation, it can lead to siloed responses and potentially delay the inclusion of internal departments, external experts, or national authorities. While islanding demonstrates a high degree of operational readiness for handling the immediate impact of an incident, this strength also has a potential vulnerability in transitioning beyond the initial technical containment, particularly concerning the necessary handovers and coordinated efforts required as the incident unfolds from being purely operational to involve IT as well.

6.2 Difficult in the intersection between IT & operations

A pattern that emerged across the utilities in our analysis was the significant friction that occurred when responsibility for incident handling shifted from operations to IT. This critical moment typically came after immediate containment actions had been carried out by operational staff, and further technical analysis, system restoration, or external reporting was required.

This handover point was frequently marked by uncertainty about roles and leadership. While the initial escalation to head of operations or a similar position had clear structures and roles, once more complex issues arose, such as the appearance of a ransomware note, coordination proved difficult. As the incident became cross-functional, complexity increased, and consequently, uncertainty about responsibilities arose. This was evident across workshops, where participants expressed uncertainty about who should initiate documentation and maintain the logbook, particularly when external IR providers were involved. It also showed in the inconsistent allocation of overall leadership of the IR, sometimes assigned to employees from operations, other times to IT, or even directly to the CEO.

This friction aligns with Michalec et al. (2022), who describe cybersecurity governance as an intersection of different *social worlds*. They frame regulation as a boundary object intended to align these different worlds. Similarly, our findings suggest that IT and operations may operate in two different social worlds, leading to clashes during the handover of a cyber incident. The NIS2 regulation, which sets new standards for cybersecurity efforts in the sector, serves as a boundary object forcing these social worlds to work towards a solution. The boundary between IT and operational responsibilities may be

defined on paper, but it hasn't stabilized into consistent, real-time coordination routines, particularly at moments like the scenario provided that require expertise from multiple social worlds with a smooth handover. Instead, these handovers often rely heavily on interpersonal familiarity and improvised, on-the-fly decisions.

This difficulty in transitioning between different responsibilities during an incident highlights the key problem that when IT and operations work in isolation, it makes responding to issues much less effective. As Gosine (2020) points out, having separate structures for IT and operations can hurt overall IR. Our study confirms this, showing that even if the operations are great at handling the initial operational side of a problem, moving to the IT aspects and managing the broader incident often becomes a weak point. Instead of a smooth handover where everyone knows their role, this transition phase often reveals a lack of shared ways of working and joint plans for cyber incidents. This means there is a need for shared IR plans or cross-training that helps manage the shift from common operational issues to cybersecurity incidents that need combined expertise. We find that this challenge is especially present in sectors like water, which naturally have a clear technical divide between IT and operations. While sorting out these internal coordination problems is important, successfully handling an incident also means working with and coordinating any necessary outside help.

6.3 Bridging existing partnerships & national help

A finding was that several utilities expressed hesitation about contacting CFCS during incidents, instead preferring to handle them internally or rely on existing relationships with experts in the form of IT suppliers, IR suppliers, or SektorCERT. These partners were consistently perceived as more approachable and better suited to help. This reluctance toward CFCS was not based on a lack of awareness, but rather on perceived usefulness, as they questioned whether CFCS would offer meaningful help in their specific situation and whether their involvement would just create more bureaucracy than value.

This preference for existing relationships stems from local rationalities, aligning with Kocksch & Jensen's (2023) argument that cybersecurity practices in SMEs are guided by direct experience, perceived relevance, and practical concerns. From this viewpoint, avoiding CFCS is seen not as non-compliance, but as a rational, experience-based judgment about the most effective course of action. Utilities often felt that CFCS lacked the specific knowledge about their setup or organization to provide effective assistance. Instead, they turned to existing relationships with whom they had close collaboration. SektorCERT is a prevalent partner due to their ongoing collaboration through monitoring and monthly reports, as well as deep insights into the sector and water systems, which give them the ability to provide quick insights into specific incidents. Similarly, IT, OT, compliance, and IR suppliers are frequently contacted for technical assistance, valued for their specialized expertise combined with knowledge of individual organizations and their

setups. Thus, CFCS was generally seen more as a body to be notified for compliance purposes, rather than a primary source of technical assistance, as they were only mentioned two times in the first actions exercise (utility D, E). Still, two utilities requested technical assistance from CFCS during the reporting. However, this was more pragmatic rather than an actual reaching out (utility D, F).

This reluctance for including CFCS reflects a broader disconnect between utilities and national agencies observed in the literature. Although in a different context, Malatji et al. (2021) observed that national agencies in the South African water sector were seen as disconnected from water and infrastructure realities. Our examination of IR practices somewhat confirms this gap, as the national agency of CFCS is perceived as being distant from the utilities and not capable of providing assistance for the water sector's unique challenges. Interestingly, Malatji et al. (2021) propose a national sector-specific CERT for the water sector that should continuously monitor the infrastructure, a role somewhat paralleled by the privately established SektorCERT in Denmark.

We found that most utilities in our sample relied more on their existing contact with actors like SektorCERT or IT vendors during cyber incidents, which were perceived as more responsive and context-aware than national authorities like CFCS. This approach is not without potential systemic risks. Hassanzadeh et al. (2020) highlight a case where national assistance was only engaged after the attack had already intensified, resulting in further damage. More broadly, they discuss how keeping IRs siloed within organizations limits the ability to create a comprehensive overview of larger attacks targeting a sector. This same pattern can be seen in the water sector from a national perspective. While the Danish preference for existing partnerships' help is grounded in practical experience and the perceived effectiveness of existing partners, the late involvement of CFCS could hinder the aggregation of threat intelligence, potentially reducing the overall national visibility of emerging threats. Although SektorCERT's widespread monitoring across the sector provides valuable insight, this function is performed by a non-governmental body. Ultimately, the reliance on sector-level responses and the hesitation to involve national authorities like CFCS could impact the sector's overall security resilience and the national capacity for a response in case of large-scale coordinated attacks.

6.4 Reputation over economy

In contrast to existing literature emphasizing financial limitations as a primary constraint for SMEs, our findings suggest that resource constraints were not a main factor driving IR decisions within the context of the studied Danish water utilities, no matter their size. While research highlights that SMEs often face significant financial resource constraints impacting their overall cybersecurity capabilities (Manzoor et al., 2024; Olonilua & Aliu, 2025; Asadi et al., 2025), our findings did not indicate this having a big impact during the IR phase. Participants consistently assigned a low priority to direct financial impacts

during incidents, focusing instead on operational continuity. This was also seen by the prioritization of systems, where economic systems were given low priority, and by related organizational considerations to downscale financial personnel in the IR teams. Although awareness of potential external costs, such as consultant fees, existed, these concerns did not appear to dictate immediate response actions.

This observed de-prioritization of direct financial considerations is likely influenced by the ownership structure of utilities. Being municipality-owned and operating under the rest in itself principle, financial concerns probably have a lower priority compared to purely private or publicly listed companies driven by profit motives or shareholder value. Any financial loss would eventually be covered by an increase in the price of water services to the consumers and the municipality.

Instead of financial concerns, we found a strong focus on their reputation. As municipality owned organizations, the utilities were highly aware of their public image and the potential reputational damage. When communicating, they were focused on controlling the narrative and preventing knowledge of the attack from prematurely leaking out. Simultaneously, they were aware of being in the public eye, as media, often local news outlets, were quick to reach out if they got a hint of a story. Furthermore, they knew from previous experience that any significant disruption to normal operations would lead to an overwhelming volume of inquiries from their users, potentially bringing down their entire organization from the administrative burden.

This combination of their organizational structure, characterized by limited direct economic incentives and enhanced political considerations, leads us to find that the utilities' concerns regarding reputational damage are substantial and often outweigh the economic consequences when executing IR.

6.5 Communication as a low priority

Olonilua et al. (2025) identified communication as a core competence in cybersecurity training, while Kumar et al. (2020) emphasized its importance in operational response. Simultaneously, many organizations rely on established frameworks for IR best practices, which typically emphasize having a communication plan without providing specific guidance on implementation during incidents. Our research confirms this tension between recognized importance and practical implementation difficulties within Danish water utilities.

Despite the recognized need for communication, it was given low priority during the workshops and was generally viewed as a support function rather than being vital to IR. This positioning somewhat contradicts the shared notion among utilities that communication is an important factor when handling incidents. This attitude was visible as most utilities struggled with their communication plans, revealing a gap between the understanding of communication's importance and practical execution capabilities.

A diversity of approaches to communication planning and execution was evident across the utilities we studied. Some organizations adopted highly engaged communication strategies that actively involved local media, maintained a social media presence, and promoted internal transparency through internal Q&A sessions. In contrast, others implemented strict confidential approaches where information was tightly controlled within the team handling the incident, with minimal disclosure both externally and internally. Despite these variations in openness, we observed communication to be an important factor among all utilities and found strong alignment regarding the sequence of communication priorities. Internal communication was universally prioritized first, followed by external stakeholders, with regulatory authorities typically addressed last, except for when compliance personnel were present.

Regarding communication within the IR team, our findings suggest that the physical dimension of communication significantly impacts IR effectiveness. Utilities consistently identified having a dedicated physical space for facilitating communication during incidents. There was consensus that a coordination meeting should be held immediately after islanding as the second action. However, tension between different organizational roles regarding meeting frequency appeared as some operational staff viewed excessive meetings as an unnecessary complication that removed resources away from technical problem-solving.

6.6 Role-specific impacts on incident response

Understanding how responsibility for cybersecurity tasks is assigned is crucial, particularly in organizations without dedicated cybersecurity departments. Kocksch and Jensen (2023) explore this, describing how different types of professionals in SMEs take on cybersecurity tasks. Their research highlights that these responsibilities are often distributed informally. We will compare our findings with theirs to reveal where ours support, challenge, or add new details to their findings.

Kocksch and Jensen (2023) found that responsibility for cybersecurity is often spread across many different roles, including IT managers, accountants, and communication staff, rather than being assigned to one central figure. Our findings confirm that responsibility is delegated to varied roles, although the type of role taking the overall lead appears context dependent. Across the utilities we studied, the overall coordinating responsibility was not consistently held by one function. While some assigned leadership from IT in the form of the head of IT or CISO, this responsibility was also held by operational leadership or by the CEO. Additionally, one utility took a different approach by assigning an external lead in the form of their IT supplier. This variation in who ultimately held the coordinating role during an incident is similar to theirs, as leadership responsibility is distributed among different potential functions or individuals, reflecting differing views on which role is best equipped to navigate complex cyber incidents.

Although having a slightly different focus, our study confirms their overall argument that the placement of cybersecurity responsibility has implications for its execution, during incidents as well. Kocksch and Jensen (2023) argue that the type of professional given cybersecurity responsibility shapes organizational practices. Our findings confirm this principle. Building on their work, we provide further insight into how different established professional roles affect cybersecurity, specifically during IR processes. In the following, we unpack the observed roles and contributions of IT professionals, financial staff, compliance personnel, communication specialists, external IT providers, and management to add depth and nuance to their findings.

Although having a slightly different focus, our study confirms Kocksch and Jensen's (2023) overall argument that cybersecurity responsibility placement impacts its execution. Building on their work, the following paragraphs will detail how roles like IT, finance, compliance, external providers, and management impact IR, adding nuance to their findings.

Our findings differ from Kocksch and Jensen's (2023) when it comes to the involvement of economic staff in IR. While they suggest that accountants can play an important role in cybersecurity due to their close collaboration with the CEO and familiarity with organizational procedures, we found that economic staff had remarkably little involvement in IR. In our study, financial and other administrative systems were often seen as less critical to operational continuity, while utilities reported that these systems could be down for days or even weeks without causing major problems impacting their core service delivery. As a result, economic staff were rarely perceived as central to the IR team. In fact, some participants even suggested removing them from future incident contingency plans because their role was not considered essential for maintaining critical operations. Furthermore, we found that the primary concerns were regarding reputation rather than economy.

One of our clearest findings regarding specific roles was that having a dedicated compliance officer made a big difference in how documentation and reporting were handled during an incident. In utilities where someone had this role, logging and reporting were integrated into the IR process from the beginning, with these staff members helping ensure reporting duties were understood and followed effectively. In contrast, utilities without compliance personnel often treated the compliance role with lower priority, leading to uncertainty about who did the reporting and how or when logging should be done. This lack of a clear mandate for documentation supports Kocksch and Jensen's (2023) observation that cybersecurity tasks are often managed informally, assigned based on availability rather than formal roles or expertise, as our findings suggest that having a compliance officer helps prevent this kind of confusion by assigning clear responsibility for this crucial task.

Kocksch and Jensen (2023) see communication specialists and compliance managers as a single group, observing that while they bring valuable communication skills and tools,

they may lack detailed familiarity with the company's core operational and administrative practices. We partly agree with their observation, but our study shows that compliance and communication roles functioned quite differently in practice during incidents, which had distinct implications for IR. When compliance officers were included early, they often played an important role in shaping how the incident was managed and reported, extending beyond just documentation. On the other hand, communication staff usually had a more limited and reactive role, mostly responsible for sharing updates with external stakeholders and generally not closely involved in core IR decision-making.

Beyond the core technical and administrative roles, high-ranking individuals such as municipal clerks, board members, and senior managers were not directly involved in the technical handling of incidents, but they still played an important role. This partly supports Kocksch and Jensen's (2023) idea that responsibility for cybersecurity is distributed across different people in an organization, extending beyond IT. However, we found that their role took on a different character as these individuals were involved not for technical reasons, but primarily because of the political and public nature of water utilities. They were often consulted to ensure that the response was perceived as legitimate and well-communicated to external stakeholders and the public. This adds a new layer to Kocksch and Jensen's (2023) findings by showing how responsibility in critical infrastructure and public organizations also includes significant symbolic and political aspects, which may be just as important for overall crisis management and organizational legitimacy as technical coordination.

Overall, our findings demonstrate that during IR in water utilities, responsibilities are more formalized and role-specific compared to the more distributed and informal patterns Kocksch and Jensen observed in everyday cybersecurity tasks within SMEs. Key roles like head of IT and compliance personnel take on perceived central responsibilities, while others, such as financial and communication staff, tend to be seen as less central to the core IR team. These patterns highlight the specific organizational context and how these matter in understanding how IR is organized and executed.

7 Limitations, further research, & implications

The following section takes a step back and offers a critical self-assessment of our project. We first address the limitations of our study to provide a clear context for our findings. Secondly, we highlight the need for further research that could advance the outcomes. Finally, we translate our insights into practical managerial implications, offering guidance for enhancing IR capabilities.

7.1 Limitations

We acknowledge that our study is subject to a number of limitations. The following section will stress some of these limitations related to our method, data collection, and analysis, followed by considerations regarding the generalizability of our findings. Understanding these limitations is crucial for the interpretation of the results and their applicability.

7.1.1 Methodological constraints

Our research relies heavily on a workshop-based approach, which introduces certain trade-offs when collecting empirical data. A primary limitation is that most of the study is based on a simulated scenario rather than real-life incidents. This means that while participants engaged with realistic situations, their responses do not fully reflect behavior under actual pressure, where factors like stress, resource constraints, and real-world consequences would be more prominent. Adding to this, the workshops were structured around best practices of IR using a cybersecurity framework rather than a formal workshop design framework. This specific structuring, while guided by domain knowledge, may have limited or shaped how participants engaged with the exercises compared to a more formally designed process.

The group setting of the workshops also presents limitations. Specifically, the dynamics within the participant groups could have influenced the collected data. We requested each utility to put a diverse team together in terms of function for the workshop. However, we assume that the discussions and outputs collected were influenced by these group settings, potentially leading some participants to withhold criticism or disagreement due to internal hierarchy, social dynamics, or a desire for consensus. Additionally, the mix of roles varied across workshops, meaning certain crucial perspectives might have been underrepresented or entirely absent in some discussions.

Facilitating the workshops came with practical challenges that impacted the data capture. Managing varying levels of participant engagement was difficult at times. Some individuals were highly active, while others were more passive. We attempted to mitigate this by directly encouraging quieter participants, rotating who was responsible for filling out forms, and dividing the group for certain tasks to balance discussions. However, cap-

turing the nuances of real-time, fast-moving group decision-making proved challenging. Unlike structured interviews, workshops involve dynamic interactions that evolve rapidly. While we used notes, photos, and recordings to reconstruct the reasoning behind actions, this reconstruction does not perfectly capture all aspects of the decisionmaking process as it unfolded organically.

Balancing our role as both facilitators and researchers required balance as we aimed to support the workshop process without influencing the outcomes. Our involvement was primarily limited to clarifying instructions or managing time. Discussions for individual tasks were allowed to unfold organically to uncover insights we might not have anticipated. However, the presence and guidance provided by us as researchers may still have shaped the direction of participant discussions, and therefore indirectly the workshop output data. Especially, the specific design as well as our framing of tasks and questions influenced how participants understood and responded, introducing bias despite our efforts to remain neutral.

Another significant limitation is present regarding the choice of the incident scenario. To generate useful data and make the workshop exercises feasible and comparable across utilities, we had to select a specific type of cyber incident. The chosen scenario involved a ransomware attack on the SRO systems, which we found through literature and expert interviews to be a common target in the sector. However, by focusing solely on this specific ransomware attack, our findings are limited to this scenario. This choice carries the risk of not fully exploring responses to other incident types. This was also a challenge highlighted by a participant stating that *"It can be extremely difficult because there can be thousands of different scenarios like this."* (Utility D). Consequently, our insights are tied to this particular kind of incident, so the applicability of our findings should be assessed when examining different cyberattacks.

7.1.2 Data collection & analytical limitations

Several data points were excluded from the paper. We undertook extensive data collection efforts, resulting in approximately 27 hours of recordings, 555 pages of transcription, and 189 pages of workshop output. We ultimately focused on a subset of data categories, excluding certain themes of collected information from the final paper. This was often due to variations in quality or relevance to the research questions. We collected data on areas which was never used such as whether utilities had cyber insurance, the specifics of their cyber contingency plans (including who could initiate them), and whether negotiation with attackers was considered a possibility. Furthermore, Insights into their considerations about worst-case scenarios for the company, customers, and business partners were also gathered, but were only used sporadically. Moreover, we were given IT policies, technical drawings, and formalized response plans from some utilities. However, since several utilities chose not to share these documents, we lacked sufficient data to make valid comparisons across all utilities. Due to the reasons mentioned, these data

points and the nuances they could provide are not included in the final paper.

We also did not systematically compare utilities based on their organizational maturity or resource levels, despite observing clear differences during the workshops. The focus of this paper is on organizational practices and execution regarding IR, rather than assessing their technical performance or maturity levels. We find that this contributes to an openness regarding this sensitive topic. However, it simultaneously limits the ability to draw conclusions about how varying levels of technical and organizational maturity specifically impact IR effectiveness.

Important external stakeholders were not directly involved in the data collection or analysis process. We did consult with industry professionals from CFCS and SektorCERT during the research and writing phase, and mentioned these organizations within the findings of the paper. However, they did not participate in the workshops or the analysis of the gathered data, which could have led to other perspectives. Furthermore, we saw how many mentioned external stakeholders like IT providers, IR providers, and the board of directors, who were also not present during the workshops. This means that the analysis primarily reflects the perspectives and experiences of the utilities themselves, potentially missing valuable insights from other stakeholders, which would likely be present during an actual incident.

Additionally, we encountered limitations related to the consistency of terminology used by participants. Individuals from different utilities or even within the same utility sometimes used different words or phrases to describe similar roles, concepts, processes, or systems. While we strived for accurate interpretation, this variation in language may have introduced some degree of uncertainty or ambiguity as we standardized some of these to allow comparison and synthesize findings across cases, potentially misinterpreting meanings.

Our choice of a cross-case analysis gave less focus to individual dynamics within cases. Our data analysis approach allowed us to examine differences and similarities across utilities and identify broader patterns. However, this focus on comparison and pattern identification across cases limited the depth to which we could examine each individual utility. While we saw each utility as an individual case, the strong emphasis on finding similarities and variations across the sample meant that less attention was necessarily given to the interplay of factors influencing IR within each single utility. Some of the detail and context-specific nuances present within individual utilities were thereby overlooked to achieve stronger qualitative generalizability through cross-case comparison.

7.1.3 Generalizability

The sample size of nine utilities represents only a portion of the Danish water sector and limits generalizability to some extent. We contacted 76 utilities within scope and successfully engaged nine, which collectively supply approximately 9% of the Danish population with water. Although the sample is extensive and includes representation

from across the country, it remains a sample of a larger population. From an academic perspective, focusing solely on Danish water utilities inherently limits how broadly the findings can be generalized to other countries or sectors with potentially different structures, regulations, or threat landscapes. Furthermore, the participating utilities likely do not represent the entire spectrum of cybersecurity maturity in the sector. We generally found that participating utilities were actively focusing on NIS2 compliance and consequently prioritized resources towards cybersecurity. This suggests that our sample might be biased towards organizations with a heightened level of cybersecurity awareness and preparedness compared to the sector average, which could have influenced the nature of the findings. Broader studies encompassing a larger and potentially more representative sample are still needed to fully understand IR across the sector.

The timing of this study is an important contextual consideration regarding the generalizability of the findings. The research was conducted in the first half of 2025, with workshops taking place as utilities were preparing for the upcoming enforcement of the NIS2 regulation. This context significantly shaped the participants' focus, as some explicitly used the workshop to test their written cybersecurity contingency plans, while others viewed it as a kickoff event for developing such materials. Consequently, the findings are situated within this specific regulatory preparation phase. Furthermore, as cybersecurity is rapidly evolving, the threat landscape in which the study was conducted, with cybercrime and Russia as main areas of concern (CFCS, 2025b), is an important context of the findings. This specific, temporal context is essential for interpreting our results, as the organizing and execution of IR will presumably change as the regulatory environment matures and the threat landscape shifts.

We believe our findings can be applied to a broader context within the EU's water sector. Specifically, our results are applicable to organizations structured similarly to ours, like the many medium-sized and publicly owned water utilities, common in a number of EU member states. Given that NIS2 is a binding directive across the EU, the regulatory context driving preparedness is shared. While the European water sector is diverse, similar organizational structures are found in countries like Germany (ATT et al., 2015), Spain (Martín Sevilla et al., 2021), Poland (Chudziński, 2018), Sweden (IBNET, 2025), the Czech Republic (Caithamlová et al., 2024), to mention a few. Therefore, our findings may offer insights with relevance for many utilities across the EU facing similar regulatory demands and operating within comparable structural conditions.

7.2 Further research

Our study provides insights into how Danish water utilities manage IR, but it also highlights promising opportunities for future research. We believe that a deeper examination of our current topics, workshop-based research, and studies at different scales would be especially valuable.

Our research has examined various themes related to IR, but the limited existing literature suggests that each area needs further exploration. For example, further studies are needed to solidify the understanding of how specific roles influence IR execution. Additionally, structured communication studies could illuminate the consequences of the more open and closed communication practices that we found. Moreover, the practical, legal, and economic implications of delegating the responsibility of systems to external partners or keeping it in-house could bring valuable insight for both academia and practice.

We find significant value in further evaluation of workshops as a research methodology for cybersecurity. The approach used in this study offers a combination of collecting data for research and providing value to the utilities. By comparing scenario-based workshops to more traditional academic methods like interviews, observations, or focus groups, as well as cybersecurity-specific methods such as tabletop exercises or digital simulations, we can gain a deeper understanding of the value they provide to both researchers and participants. These studies could possibly validate workshop-based research as a robust and effective methodology for examining IR.

Finally, exploring IR research at varying scales could bring significant insights. On a smaller scale, ethnographic or observational studies during real or simulated incidents could uncover nuanced details about behavior, communication breakdowns, and decision-making under pressure, which are elements that are difficult to capture in structured workshops. Conversely, at a larger scale, there's an opportunity for more systemic research into knowledge flow within the sector. This could involve investigating how lessons learned from one utility are (or are not) shared with others, and the role of organizations like DANVA or SektorCERT in fostering sector-wide learning and standardization. Comparing utilities across different EU countries could also reveal how local policy environments, sector structure, and cybersecurity maturity levels influence IR preparedness. Alternatively, comparing our findings to those of other sectors could provide broader insights. A longitudinal study, returning to the same utilities in 1–2 years, would also be beneficial to assess changes in IR procedures, roles, or awareness, particularly given the upcoming deadline for NIS2 implementation.

7.3 Managerial implications

Our findings offer several practical insights for managers working in or with Danish water utilities. While the study is rooted in structured workshops and simulated scenarios, the themes and challenges observed point to real organizational dynamics that may still support managerial decision-making.

1) IR teams should reflect organizational priorities

We observed differences in incident leadership, with the Head of IT, Head of Operations, or even the CEO taking charge. Furthermore, the inclusion of roles, such as for

economic, compliance, and communication functions, had a great impact on IR practices and influenced what was prioritized.

Based on this, we suggest that the management do not just appoint IR leads based on titles or availability. Choose your team based on what your utility needs during a crisis. If public trust is your biggest concern, communication staff need a seat at the table. If compliance or technical recovery is key, adjust accordingly. These roles should be documented clearly, not decided ad hoc.

2) Leverage existing operational alertness

In most workshops, it was operational staff who acted first. Their ability to quickly isolate affected systems often gave the organization valuable time, but their role in IR wasn't always formally written down.

Our advice for the industry is to recognize and build on what is already happening on the ground. Make space for operational staff in your IR plans. Provide clear escalation points and define how their early actions fit into the bigger picture. Their instincts are strong. Your plans should support them, not sideline them.

3) Clear responsibilities between IT and Operations

A common stumbling block came when an incident moved from operations into IT's hands. We found that there were areas that had not been discussed before, which could create confusion about who did what and lead to delays or overlaps during IR.

To overcome this, we suggest that the transition between operations and IT should be clearly mapped out and rehearsed. Everyone should know what to deliver, when to hand over, what to expect from the other side, and how to coordinate across the gap. If this is not clear before an incident, it could cause big problems during a real one.

4) Communication planning not as an afterthought

Reputation came up again and again, also more often than the financial impact. Still, only a few utilities had thought through who would communicate during a crisis, what they would communicate, and when.

Our advice for approaching this is to make communication a core part of your IR planning. Have message templates, a contact list of internal and external stakeholders, and clear spokesperson roles. Decide in advance how to handle the pressure that comes internally or from the public, and give communication staff the time and space to lead in this area.

5) Incident response should practiced

During the study, we saw how some utilities had detailed contingency plans. Others were still working on it, or had one which only some had read. But what really mattered was whether people had used the plan before. Those who had run through it recently or even just once showed more confidence, coordination, and speed. For IR, having a plan is not enough.

Test it. Talk through it. Run a tabletop exercise or arrange a real physical test. Make sure the people involved know what to do and when. When things go wrong, practice is what people fall back on.

8 Conclusion

In this paper, we have examined an area of cybersecurity within critical infrastructure. Specifically, we have examined the area of incident response within the Danish water sector guided by the question: *How do Danish water utilities organize and execute cybersecurity incident response, and what patterns of practice and challenges emerge?*

To answer this, we conducted nine on-site, scenario-based workshops with Danish water utilities that collectively supply 9% of the Danish population. This approach allowed for the collection of rich, comparable data through structured outputs and audio recordings, which were then systematically analyzed using a cross-case method to reveal patterns both within-cases and across-cases.

We found that the sector showed a strong capacity for initial IR, primarily through rapid islanding practices. This proficiency likely came from operational personnel's familiarity with alert-based work patterns. However, significant difficulties consistently arose at the intersection of IT and operations, where a lack of coordination routines created obstacles when the incident shifted hands from operational staff to IT staff. Utilities also demonstrated a general preference for contacting existing partnerships over national assistance, driven by perceived relevance and capacity to help.

In part due to their organizational structure, we observed that Danish water utilities mainly focus on reputational considerations rather than the direct economic consequences of a cyberattack. Adding to this, we found that communication, although it was frequently stated as a high priority, struggled in practical implementation. Consistent patterns emerged in prioritizing internal communication before external. However, the openness of communication varied widely among utilities.

Our findings indicate that the roles included in the core IR team significantly affect IR capabilities. Leadership is often delegated to roles related to IT, OT, or directly to the CEO. Our findings also suggest that the roles included in the process of handling an incident matter a great deal in practice. The inclusion of roles such as economic, compliance, and communication functions affects the IR practices and has distinct implication for a utility's IR execution.

Moving forward, strengthening the cybersecurity posture of critical infrastructure like the water sector demands not only technical solutions but also an understanding of organizational structure, processes, and responsibilities. Addressing these aspects will be crucial for enhancing resilience as the threat landscape continues to evolve.

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